

B-Shapes

Borders Shaping Perceptions of European Societies

Work package 6: Policy and governance - integrating perceptions of borderland citizens into responsive policymaking

Cultural and cultural heritage policies in border regions

Internal report based on WP6 desktop work for task 6.1.

Sara Svensson, Oriana Miraka, Tomas Nilson

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1. Introduction

1.1. Contribution to policy and practice

This internal report provides a comprehensive analysis of cultural and cultural heritage policies of relevance in the border regions included in the B-shapes project. Each B-shapes partner has contributed based on their respective area and profile expertise (T6.1). The report contributes to reaching the B-shapes objectives to map the extent to which European and regional heritage policies are integrated into regional development activities and every-day policymaking in borderlands (B-shapes objective O6.2). The compilation is intended to aid the development of policy scenarios and policy recommendations (Task 6.2 and Task 6.6.). Collecting policy summaries concerning cultural heritage, regional development, and cross-border cooperation across the varied regions and areas of expertise in the B-SHAPES project will also foster a nuanced comprehension of policy landscapes, facilitating informed decision-making processes.

1.2. Contribution to state-of-the-art in academic research

In addition to the field of policy, this report has the potential to contribute to several strands of academic literature, dealing respectively with cultural policy & cultural heritage policy¹ and border studies, globally and in Europe). Bridging the *gap* between these, the report is the basis for creating a connection where they intersect.

Recent key works of relevance to this nexus include but are not limited to:

Prokkola et al. 2024²: The study comprises three Northern European border regions and shows through a study of destination homepages and destination brochures that even in a region characterized by good communication systems and relations, competition over tourists and cultural differences prevent cohesive cross-border approaches. “Hence, although EU tourism policy documents emphasize tourism that can foster economic growth and employment in many border regions and how collaborative tourism development can strengthen the sense of European togetherness, national and local tourism development policies often underline different standpoints. There seems to be little evidence of the transformation of European border regions into cross-border destinations at a wider scale, and the pandemic experience may further delay such a vision from coming true.” (p. 16)

Durand 2022³: The paper examines Interreg funding over a 20-year period (2000-2020) to see how it contributed to helping with cross-border cultural co-operation. The conclusions are that border

¹ Examples of studies include: (1) Čeginskas, V. L. A., Kaasik-Krogerus, S., Lähdesmäki, T., & Mäkinen, K. (2021). Constructing social Europe through European cultural heritage. *European Societies*, 23(4), 487–512; (2) Cicerchia, A. (2019). Evidence-Based Policy Making for Cultural Heritage. *SCIRES-IT*, 9(1), 99–108.; (3) Nilsson, B. (2022). An ideology-critical examination of the cultural heritage policies of the Sweden Democrats. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HERITAGE STUDIES*, 28(5), 622–634; (4) Renko, V., Johannisson, J., Kangas, A., & Blomgren, R. (2022). Pursuing decentralisation: regional cultural policies in Finland and Sweden. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 28(3), 342–358.

² Prokkola, E. K., Andersen, D. J., Jakola, F., Nilson, T., & Svensson, S. M. H. (2024). Multilayered Borders as a Method for Studying Tourism Destinations: A Case of Northern European Border Regions. *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 1-21.

³ Frédéric Durand (2022) What types of cultural cooperation exist in European cross-border areas?, *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography*, 104:4, 307-326, DOI: 10.1080/04353684.2021.2015245

regions vary in the importance they give cultural, as opposed to economic, co-operation and that tourism has been the most common area for co-operation (the author suggests that “social and identity issues” should be given greater importance). Also, municipal authorities were the main drivers of this co-operation, whereas cultural institutions are largely missing.

Bakry & Growe 2021⁴: This article used the trilateral Upper Rhine region as a case study to explore how cultural networks work between metropolitan areas in borderlands and concludes that it is an important topic for the EU to consider when it comes to policy. The article found a significant amount of cultural linkages across borders, but nonetheless concluded that presence of borders negatively the number of connections across borders.

Older studies of interest include:

Lois-González, Palmeiro-Piñeiro & Pazos-Ot’ón 2007⁵: The article looks at the relationship between Galicia (in Spain) and Northern Portugal as an example of a European cross-border area with important cultural ties and talks about “transboundary identity.” The conclusion is that whether a person feels a stronger identity to the region or to their nation-state varies throughout the border area. In linking their findings to Europe more broadly, the authors argue that it is important that identity in border areas is promoted from a local level.

Eskilsson & Högdahl 2009⁶: The paper investigates cultural heritage in terms of marketing and promoting a particular place, using the Snapphane people in the Öresund region as an example. While not focusing on policy, the paper incorporates political dimensions to cultural heritage.

Perrin 2010⁷: The paper discusses Euroregions, i.e., associations of municipalities and regions, and how countries within a region can collaborate on cross-border cultural policy. Two case studies are mentioned: Pyrenees-Mediterranean (France-Spain) and the ‘Grand’ Region (Belgium, France, Luxembourg, and Germany).

Mehn 2020⁸: This edited volume contains reflections from scholars of different disciplines on the intersection between heritage and borders. Notable contributions include a chapter by Péter Balogh on the revival of cultural heritage borders and a chapter by Elisabeth Niklasson on the European heritage label and borders.

⁴ Bakry, A., & Growe, A. (2021). Analysing cultural networks in cross-border metropolitan regions. The case of the Upper Rhine region (Germany–Switzerland–France). *Erdkunde*, 75(3), 169-190.

⁵ Lois-González, R. C., Palmeiro-Piñeiro, J. L., & Pazos-Ot’ón, M. (2007). Integration, Memory and Cultural Heritage in Galicia-Northern Portugal Border Region. *Nordia Geographical Publications*, 36(4), 23–34.

⁶ Eskilsson, L., & Högdahl, E. (2009). Cultural Heritage across Borders? – Framing and Challenging the Snapphane Story in Southern Sweden. *Scandinavian Journal of Hospitality and Tourism*, 9(1), 65–80.

⁷ Perrin, T. (2010). Inter-territoriality as a new trend in cultural policy? The case of Euroregions. *Cultural Trends*, 19(1–2), 125–139. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09548961003696153>

1.3. Terminology and structure

Before proceeding, two notes on terminology and how this report has been structured.

We use the word policy broadly, referring to different document types such as laws, strategies, guidelines, etc. Terminology in other languages will vary depending on public administrative history and competence allocation between different levels and branches of government.

The research of the B-shapes project covers 10 bilateral borders. However, in 2 cases, these bilateral relationships are interwoven into trilateral border regions (Czechia-Germany-Poland and Bulgaria-Greece-Turkey). In this report, the analysis is divided into one section covering these bilateral or trilateral regions. The order is north to south, with the names of the countries constituting them in alphabetical order. An initial note expands the explanation of what constitutes a border region.

2. Finland - Sweden

2.1. Context

The Tornio River Valley (Tornio-Haparanda border region) has historically formed a culturally, politically, and economically united region and forms a solid landscape area characterized by the Tornio River, typical natural environment, and villages and settlements built along the river valley. Except for the war times, mobility across the border has been relatively free, and people's everyday lives are in many ways built on this free interaction. The border between Finland and Sweden has been seen as the "world's most peaceful border," and in the landscape, the border is mainly invisible, or it is made visible through specific infrastructure and artwork, like in the twin city Tornio-Haparanda. Both countries are unitary states where relevant policies could potentially be found at national, regional, and local levels.

2.2. Description of policies

Seven relevant policies were identified. On the Finnish side, the national, regional and local levels were covered, whereas the Swedish ones were on regional and local level. One cross-border document was analyzed.

For the Finnish national policy *Valtakunnallisesti arvokkaat maisema-alueet* (Nationally valuable landscape areas 2021), nationally valuable landscape areas are being inventoried for cultural environment protection and conservation. Inventory is based on the Land Use and Building Act (132/1999), which requires "ensuring that the values of nationally valuable cultural environments and natural heritage are safeguarded." The value of these cultural landscapes is based on the synergy of natural heritage and traditional land use (especially cultivation and building) (Finnish Government 2021). The purpose of the inventory of these nationally significant built cultural heritage sites and nationally significant archaeological sites is to "form the knowledge base" for acknowledging the cultural environment values "in accordance with the national land use objectives." The inventory of the nationally valuable landscape areas covers the whole of Finland and is based on the Land Use and Building Act (132/1999). The inventory should be considered in all forms of land use planning. In the press release, it is emphasized that to sustain the value of these cultural landscapes requires a) cooperation based on the continuity of traditional livelihoods, b) respect for the cultural and natural values that characterize the regions, and c) skillful land use planning (Finnish Government 2021). The document does not, however, describe more specifically how this should be done.

The goal of the regional program *Joen ja meren rajakaupunki: Tornion kulttuuriympäristöohjelma* (The Program for Cultural Environment in Tornio, 2012) is to support both land use planning and other planning activities, as well as strengthen the local identity and consciousness of local citizens on their everyday environment. The program emphasizes the increased recognition and importance of cultural heritage both from the perspective of environmental conservation and regional development (regional identity, competitiveness). The program for a cultural environment in Tornio evaluates the state of the cultural environment and describes its development

throughout time. Several key stakeholders are involved in the program: it is made together with The Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment of Lapland (ELY-center of Lapland) and the City of Tornio. ELY-centers operate under the central government, and they are responsible for different regional implementation and development tasks. Other key stakeholders involved are regional museums, the Finnish Heritage Agency, the Ministry of Environment, and Metsähallitus (state-owned). The project is funded by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and published by the Ministry of Environment of Finland. The involvement of different governmental levels emphasizes the interconnections in the conservation sector covered by the legislation. (There exists no separate cultural environment program on a regional level in Lapland vs. Norrbotten). For implementation, the program emphasizes especially the role of local/regional organizations and associations as well as individual property- and landowners. However, it is obvious that the City of Tornio and other organizations involved in land use planning are also key stakeholders. To achieve its objectives, the document underlines the responsibility of local/regional actors and individuals as well as the different support services and funding offered by officials. Regional and state officials help, advise, and guide with the issues related to the conservation of the cultural environment. They also grant different funding in-kind. Strengthening the co-operation between different administrative branches and offering help for village associations, different clubs, and other associations and individuals (e.g., communal repair and maintenance voluntary work and events)

The main objectives/goals of the regional policy *Lappi-sopimus, Lapin maakuntaohjelma 2022-2025* (The development program for Lapland) is done by the Regional Council of Lapland, and it is the main regional development strategy document. The strategy describes the current state of regional development of Lapland and sets the development goals for future development and planning. There are seven goals, of which one - the last one - relates to the question of cultural heritage. This is “the vitality of Sami culture”. The strategy mentions that Lapland covers various cultural and regional characteristics, which together form a diverse and rich Lappish culture. However, more precisely, cultural heritage is discussed only in the context of Sami. The cultural heritage of the Sami people is discussed from the perspective of both land/traditional land use and immaterial cultural heritage. It is stated that Sami people have a legislative right to sustain and develop their language and culture. The section concerning Sami culture is prepared by the Sami Parliament. The key stakeholders involved in the policy development are the Sami Parliament and the Regional Council of Lapland, and the latter is responsible for implementing the policy and the Sami municipalities (municipalities covering Sapmi). In general, the implementation section is written in passive form and does not specify more precisely who the key stakeholders’ actors are for the implementation. It does, however, talk about “regional actors,” which includes at least private sector actors (especially mining and forest industry companies and the tourism industry). To achieve its objectives, there is a long list of different actions how to “sustain the vitality of Sami culture,” which are linked – among others - to the legislative rights, development of traditional livelihoods (including environmental conservation), and combining these with tourism and other business sectors, as well as sustaining and developing Sami language and culture.

The policy of the Swedish *Norrbottens kulturmiljöprogram 2010-2020* (Cultural-environment programme of the region of Norrbotten) outlines the cultural profile of the Norrbotten region, highlighting the characteristics of its landscape and settlement. It emphasizes that the program should be applicable both regionally and locally, with the goal of positively impacting the cultural environment in Norrbotten. The policy aims to identify valuable cultural environments that should continue to receive attention, serve as a foundation for achieving environmental goals, support

development initiatives based on cultural heritage, and foster discussions and increased awareness of Norrbotten's cultural environments. Key stakeholders include local and regional actors such as regional councils and municipalities across the Norrbotten region. To achieve the stated objectives, the program serves as a basis for planning and supports regional development. The program identifies around 200 cultural environments that need to be prioritized from a regional perspective for efforts regarding conservation, documentation, information, and accessibility.

The regional *development strategy of Region Norrbotten* (Regional Utvecklingsstrategi Norrbotten 2030) aims to offer guidelines for regional development and growth. It describes how the region is developed. The document offers a vision of Norrbotten as the most welcoming and innovative region. The document also identifies and discusses megatrends that impact the development of Norrbotten. The document pays considerable attention to women and minorities. Especially the Sami people. Regional cultural heritage and landscape are presented as an asset of regional development and attractiveness. There is a section called "Nature, culture and free time for everyone" that addresses efforts to preserve, develop, and make available natural and cultural environments, promote a business life through the creation of innovative environments based on culture and cultural heritage as well as make available and secure long-term management of culture, natural and cultural environments and strengthen culture infrastructure. The key stakeholders are the regional authorities (Region Norrbotten). It seems that the strategy is rather top-down, or at least it does not describe how different stakeholders are involved.

By bringing together different people and actors, the aims of the policy can be achieved. The document sets a frame for the work that should be done together to develop the region. It is stated that the process and development work need to be inclusive, open, empower citizens' trust and confidence, and inspire dialogue and cooperation about Norrbotten's development. Means to develop the region include strengthening Norrbotten's brand and creating attractive knowledge and stories about the county. The development of cooperation between businesses, academia, the public sector, and civil society is seen as a means to get more young people to choose Norrbotten for their studies and work.

At the local level, the Cultural Plan of the Swedish Haparanda Municipality 2013-2015 (*Kulturplan Haparanda kommun: Plan for Culture, Haparanda Municipality*) was analyzed. The document offers an overview of the goals and activities in the municipality. The main objective of the plan was to increase the participation of people in culture (policy) in the municipality and gain new ideas from people. Cultural heritage and its joint development in the municipality are a core issue of the plan. Cultural sites (art, museums) of the municipality are described. The document takes culture as a mean to bring people together and develop new initiatives with different groups of people (including schools) as its objective. The strategy highlights several key areas for development. It focuses on cooperation with financiers, strengthening associational life, and enhancing democratic engagement among young people. There is an emphasis on ensuring young people's access to culture through schools and increasing the city's art and decorations. Efforts are also aimed at increasing residents' knowledge of their history to foster pride in the citizens of Haparanda. Special grants and funding for study associations are mentioned, along with initiatives to promote and strengthen cultural industries.

2.3. The cross-border dimension

In the case of southern Lapland's and Aavasaksa's cultural landscape, the border river between Finland and Sweden, Tornio River, is presented as a focal element of the landscape. The Tornio River Valley is seen as a coherent cultural landscape which entails settlements on both sides of the river. The history of the border drawing is also described in the document. However, the actual sites on the Swedish river are not named or described. In the case of Aavasaksa's cultural landscape, the border bridge is mentioned several times, is seen as an important element of the landscape, and underlines the cross-border dimensions of the area.

The Program for Cultural Environment in Tornio, 2012, includes sites in its inventory that are either on the border or on the Swedish side (Victoria square, boundary stones). However, the overall inventory is made from the Finnish national (Tornio) perspective, and the cross-border perspective is very small. In addition, the strategy describes both the history of the Tornio city and the overall history of the Tornio Valley. The strategy underlines that the common history and border drawing create the special characteristics of cultural heritage in Tornio. The history of many of the inventoried sites dates back to when Finland was under Swedish rule. Although the document states that cultural heritage has an important role in regional development and regional competitiveness, the actual contribution of the program may stay rather limited as it does not specify specific actions. Finally, among the Finnish documents, the strategy has a regional-national perspective, and cross-border dimensions are not relevant. In the context of Sami culture, there is a mention that "the work for lowering the border obstacles and strengthening the cross-border co-operation needs to be continued." However, the sentence remains rather detached as it does not further elaborate or describe what these "border obstacles" are in this context. Also, when it comes to overall goals of regional development, economic growth, or social cohesion, a cross-border dimension is lacking as the policy is done from a regional(national) perspective. The fact that the Sami region also covers areas from northern Sweden, Norway, and the Kola peninsula in Russia is not mentioned.

In contrast, the Swedish documents either lack cross-border dimensions or they are vaguely referred to. The Cultural-environment programme of the region of Norrbotten) outlines lacks cross-border dimensions, it is largely nationally and regionally oriented. It forgoes direct cross-border references. In the context of Haparanda municipality, the history as a border town is described but the perspective is national. Likewise, the regional *development strategy of Region Norrbotten* lacks a cross-border dimension for the overall goals of cross-border regional development, economic growth, and social cohesion, even though a vision exists. Transnational and cross-border connections are mentioned only a few times as opportunities. It has a national and regional perspective. Transport connections to Finland (Uleåborg) are mentioned briefly.

Even though the Cultural Plan of the Swedish Haparanda Municipality mentions a cross-border regional dimension and cultural heritage attractions located on the other side of the border, the document has no direct cross-border dimension. It has a local-national perspective. Yet the document includes a cross-border logo, featuring both the Tornio and the Haparanda names. The impression is that there are cases where the policy would have been relevant, e.g., adopted, applied, referred to, in a cross-border context, but such a context is not developed even if many activities could have included "the other side." The perspective is national and local, also when the border is mentioned or when it comes to the policy's capacity to contribute to the overall goals of cross-border regional development, economic growth, or social cohesion.

2.4. Alignment with EU policies

With regards to the Finnish side landscape inventory entirely lacks references to EU and international policies. The municipal and the regional documents, on the other hand, have references. The Program for Cultural Environment in Tornio refers to the European Council's three conventions related to cultural environment and heritage: Convention for the Protection of the Architectural Heritage of Europe (Granada, 1985); Convention for the Protection of the Archaeological Heritage of Europe (Valletta, 1992); The European Landscape Convention (Florence, 2000). In addition, the document mentions that The European Union funds projects related to the cultural environment through Structural Funds that "the impact of many directives extends to the building heritage." There are also other policies aligned with the document - after introducing the Finnish legislation related to cultural heritage, the strategy presents some international conventions and guidelines. *International agreements and recommendations, such as UNESCO and the Haag Convention of 1954*, contribute to the obligations and starting points for taking care of the cultural environment. The regional policy states that Finland has fulfilled its international obligations towards the European Union's only indigenous people. It does not, however, specify what this includes in the document. Other policy alignments related to cultural heritage preservation or management include the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, which is declared to form a global framework when the strategy is being put into practice.

The Swedish documents only mention the international context in passing, such as references to Natura 2000, the UN Sustainable Development agenda, or Interreg.

3. Denmark - Sweden

3.1. Context

The Oresund region can be defined in different ways, for instance, consisting of the territories of Sjaelland and Scania, but different definitions are to be found in daily speech, newspaper articles, television, and academic texts. For the purpose of the B-shapes project, we also consider the Halland region and part of the North Jutland Region to be part of the region on the grounds that it is the closest Danish region to Halland. Relevant policies in both countries can be found at all three levels of government: national, regional, and local. In Sweden, though, the emphasis was on the local and regional level, whereas in Denmark, there was more emphasis on the national level. Notably, the main institutional structure for cross-border cooperation, the Greater Copenhagen Committee, does not include culture (or people-to-people contacts) among its activities, meaning that politically driven cross-border cooperation in this area is lacking.

3.2. Description of policies

Thirteen relevant policies were identified and analyzed:

Seven Danish policies at a national level were found relevant and analyzed. The main aim of the Danish "**Promulgation of the Act on Building Preservation and the Conservation of Buildings and Urban Environments**" is to protect and preserve Denmark's important historical and cultural buildings and urban areas. The policy aims to safeguard buildings and urban areas that have significant historical, architectural, or cultural value. This is done by officially designating these buildings and areas as protected, ensuring that they are preserved for future generations. The policy outlines a strategic approach allowing the Ministry of Culture to designate buildings and urban environments as protected based on their cultural and historical significance. The policy mandates that any alterations or demolitions of such protected structures require prior approval from the Ministry. Furthermore, it includes provisions for financial support for maintaining and restoring protected sites, ensuring their ongoing preservation.

The principal aim of the "**Announcement on the Special Building Inspection**" is to establish and govern the operations of Det Særlige Bygningssyn (The Special Building Conservation Council), a crucial entity in the preservation of Denmark's architectural heritage. The policy ensures the proper composition of this body, with members possessing relevant expertise in architecture, cultural history, and conservation. In doing so, it directly addresses the preservation of cultural heritage by providing oversight and decision-making authority on matters pertaining to the conservation of significant buildings and urban environments. The policy explains how Det Særlige Bygningssyn is structured and operates, including how its members are appointed, how decisions are made, and the procedures for dealing with building conservation cases. By ensuring that a council of experts makes decisions, the policy helps to support well-informed and strategic conservation efforts. Additionally, the Sekretariat, under the Slot- og Kulturstyrelsen, assists the Council by ensuring that administrative tasks and case management are handled efficiently.

The **Announcement on the Delegation of Tasks and Powers to the Heritage Agency of Denmark** policy aims to give the Danish Agency for Culture and Palaces (Kulturarvsstyrelsen) specific tasks and authority to oversee cultural heritage laws. This includes preserving buildings, urban areas, and museum-related legislation. The policy ensures that the Agency has the power to manage Denmark's cultural heritage, including laws for protecting and maintaining heritage buildings and museum collections.

The **Act Amending the Act on the Protection of Cultural Assets in Denmark** policy aims to revise the current law regarding the protection of cultural values in Denmark, with a specific emphasis on addressing the illegal importation of cultural objects. The policy proposes more stringent penalties, such as fines and imprisonment, for individuals involved in the importation of cultural goods that have been unlawfully taken out of their country of origin. This amendment aims to enhance Denmark's legal framework to provide better protection for cultural heritage by preventing illegally exported cultural items from entering the country and facilitating their return to their rightful place.

The Promulgation of the Act on Support for Non-Formal Adult Education, Voluntary Non-Formal Association Activities, and Folk High Schools, as well as on the People's University (the Non-Formal Education Act), provides financial support and structural frameworks for adult education, voluntary association work, day high schools, and the Folk University (Folkeuniversitetet) in Denmark. The policy aims to promote democratic understanding, active citizenship, and cultural awareness among the population by supporting educational activities that are rooted in democratic values and the cultural heritage of Denmark.

The Act on Certain Media Service Providers' Contributions to the Promotion of Danish Culture has as its objective to strengthen the production of Danish audiovisual content, such as films, series, and documentaries, by requiring certain media service providers to contribute financially to the promotion of Danish culture. This law aims to ensure that there is a sustainable production of high-quality Danish content that reflects and promotes the nation's cultural heritage.

At the Danish sub-national level, three policies were analyzed. **The cultural policy of Helsingør Municipality, called "Culture that Makes a Difference,"** was approved on May 30, 2023. It aims to use culture to promote growth, development, and community well-being. The policy focuses on enhancing community cohesion, engaging youth, boosting economic growth, preserving everyday culture, promoting sustainable development, and fostering innovation and experimentation. The policy aims to make Helsingør a leading cultural municipality in Denmark and gain recognition on a European scale. It seeks to build on the city's strengths, such as its rich historical heritage, vibrant cultural institutions, and active civil society, to create a strong cultural environment. It also seeks to integrate cultural heritage into daily life, making it accessible to all citizens. This includes preserving and promoting the city's historical sites, supporting local cultural institutions, and ensuring that cultural activities are inclusive and reach diverse audiences. The **Aalborg Municipality's Cultural Policy** is designed to strengthen the city's cultural landscape. It emphasizes the integration of culture into urban development and the encouragement of artistic innovation. The policy also aims to support local cultural institutions while ensuring cultural accessibility for everyone. To achieve its objectives, the policy includes specific strategies. It aims to support local artists and cultural institutions, ensuring they thrive

and contribute to the city's cultural vibrancy. Cultural programs are designed to reach all residents, with a focus on youth and underrepresented groups. The policy also promotes partnerships between cultural sectors and other fields such as health and education. Finally, it seeks to create opportunities for public cultural events and performances in urban spaces, enriching the city's public life and fostering community engagement. The primary goal of the **(Cultural Agreement 2021-2024)**, a document originating with the Danish Ministry of Culture in collaboration with regions, is to strengthen regional cultural cooperation and support cultural initiatives that promote local identity, access to culture, and cultural diversity. The policy focuses on enhancing cultural heritage through public engagement and innovation in cultural practices. The policy outlines several actions to be taken, including the support of local cultural projects, facilitating public access to cultural activities, promoting partnerships between public and private sectors, encouraging innovation in digital and artistic platforms and enhancing cultural education and youth involvement in cultural activities.

On the Swedish side, no relevant national policies were identified, but two regional and two local policies were analyzed. **The Regional Cultural Plan for Skåne 2021–2024** outlines the strategic direction for cultural development, aligning with national and regional policy objectives. The plan is based on three principles: the intrinsic value of culture, its democratic foundation, and its societal role. Integrated into the "Open Skåne 2030" strategy, the plan addresses Scania's challenges and promotes sustainable development. It requires collaboration across governmental, business, non-profit, and academic sectors.

The Halland Cultural Policy Plan 2025–2028 aims to achieve three overarching cultural policy goals, which are a vibrant and bold hub for culture, a community where everyone can engage in cultural activities, and a society enriched by culture. It is connected to the strategic development areas of artistic creation, engaging cultural life for everyone and culture as a social force. The cultural strategy spans from 2025 to 2032 and will be implemented through two four-year cultural plans. This document outlines the first of these plans.

Two periodic cultural policy plans for Malmö were analyzed: the **Malmö Cultural Strategy 2014–2020** and the **Cultural Strategic Program 2024–2030**. The Malmö Cultural Strategy 2014–2020 is structured around the idea that art and culture are pivotal to the city's socioeconomic development. The strategy seeks to incorporate cultural practices as a mechanism for fostering sustainability, creativity, and democracy within Malmö. The policy focuses on enhancing cultural ecosystems by providing financial and infrastructural support to local cultural organizations. It emphasizes advancing cultural freedom and participation, making artistic expression accessible to all, with a particular focus on marginalized communities. Additionally, the policy seeks to ensure equitable access to cultural resources by removing barriers to participation and creating inclusive spaces for cultural activities across all city districts. By incorporating cultural aspects into urban planning and public spaces, the policy wants to embed cultural heritage and creative practices into the daily lives of residents, positioning culture as a core element of urban development rather than a separate entity. The Cultural Strategic Program 2024-2030 is an updated version, stressing the importance of art and culture in shaping Malmö's future, ensuring that they contribute to the city's growth and identity, and is divided into 4 strategic aims: strengthening cultural ecosystems; promoting cultural freedom and participation; Ensuring equal access to culture; Integrating culture into urban planning and public spaces.

3.3. The cross-border dimension

While Danish policies at national level occasionally include references to other countries, they generally do not explicitly mention a local cross-border dimension. An exception is the **Announcement on the Special Building Inspection, which** has a specific focus on the cultural heritage within Denmark and its national context; it also acknowledges the potential cross-border dimension in heritage conservation efforts. It highlights the possibility of collaborative initiatives in heritage conservation with neighboring countries that have similar cultural or architectural heritage. Neighboring countries could include Sweden and its southernmost regions, which constitute part of the border region.

Some of the sub-national strategies, on the other hand, pay attention to regional border issues. Helsingør Municipality's cultural policy focuses on working with neighboring regions, especially across the Øresund, to collaborate on cultural projects, festivals, and partnerships. They also want to promote Helsingør as a great tourist cultural destination and encourage international cultural exchange. The policy includes hosting events like the Shakespeare Festival and the PASSAGE Festival and improving cultural infrastructure such as Kulturhavnen and cultural venues. They aim to attract international visitors by highlighting Helsingør's historical and maritime heritage, including attractions like Kronborg Castle. Ultimately, they want to position Helsingør as a leading cultural hub in the Nordic region, driving regional development, economic growth, and social cohesion through cross-border cultural activities. The cultural strategy of the Swedish region of Scania aims to strengthen cooperation within the Öresund region and maintain close connections with the Baltic Sea area, Germany, and the rest of Europe. This is mentioned three times in the policy. It states, for instance, that "The European dimension and cooperation in the Öresund region shall be essential elements of the cultural policy in Skåne" (page 71) and that Scania "will strengthen cooperation within the Öresund region and be closely connected with the Baltic Sea area, Germany, and the rest of Europe." The Danish Cultural Agreement supports cross-border cultural projects through collaborations with neighboring countries and, importantly, regional partnerships. The Malmö documents emphasize and partnerships with neighboring countries, especially Denmark, to foster cultural exchange and cooperation. Malmö's geographic location within the Öresund Region is expected to facilitate these cross-border interactions, further enhancing its role as a center for regional cultural innovation.

3.4. Alignment with EU policies

Some of the Danish national policies are closely aligned with EU policies, such as the ones on protection of cultural assets which refers to the European Parliament and Council Regulation (EU) 2019/880 concerning the importation of cultural goods, and the policy on Media Service Providers' Contributions to the Promotion of Danish Culture which explicitly aligns with the EU's AVMS (Audiovisual Media Services) Directive, particularly with its provisions that allow member states to impose financial contributions on media service providers targeting their audiences. The law ensures compliance with EU regulations while promoting the production of European, particularly Danish, content. Other relevant international policies that are referred to include UNESCO.

The sub-national policies contain fewer references. For instance, the cultural policy of Helsingør does not explicitly reference EU directives, but its emphasis on sustainable development and social cohesion aligns with broader European goals. The language and approach suggest an adherence to principles found in EU cultural policies, such as inclusivity, accessibility, and the

promotion of cultural diversity. Additionally, the policy's focus on international collaboration and cultural exchange points to an alignment with international conventions on cultural heritage preservation, such as those promoted by UNESCO. This alignment is inferred through the policy's commitment to fostering international cultural partnerships and preserving cultural heritage, which are key aspects of many international cultural agreements. The Scania regional policy makes no direct references to EU directives or policies, but "Europe" is mentioned several times. It also has an international outlook containing information that the cultural heritage sector functions by collecting, processing, and disseminating knowledge about cultural heritage and archives, following the regulations of ICOM (International Council of Museums) and ICA (International Council on Archives). Halland's regional cultural policy is in harmony with several international conventions and agreements concerning the preservation and management of cultural heritage. Specifically, it upholds the UN's International Convention on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights, affirming the right to freely engage in cultural life and artistic expression. This aligns with UNESCO's principles under the World Heritage Convention and the Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage. Region Halland's legislative framework, including the Libraries Act (2013:801) and the Museum Act (2017:563), reinforces these global commitments by governing and promoting cultural institutions in Sweden. Moreover, the Act (2018:1197) on the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child underscores children's entitlement to participate in cultural and artistic pursuits, supporting international endeavors to preserve and enhance cultural heritage for future generations. The European Landscape Convention underscores that landscapes represent a shared asset and responsibility, encompassing diverse cultural, ecological, aesthetic, social, and economic values. Its goal is to cultivate a more enriching living environment where everyone can actively contribute to its development.

4. Denmark - Germany

4.1. Context

For the purpose of the B-shapes project, the Danish-German border region consists of Sønderjylland-Schleswig (South and North Schleswig). Relevant policies in the Danish context are found at the national level in DK (centralized state, legal and policy framework stipulated by the state) and the level of municipalities (*kommuner*). In the German context, the cultural heritage of the state Schleswig-Holstein provides the framework conditions for the lower governance levels, which are Kreis, Stadt, and Gemeinde (from now on referred to as municipalities even when this does not entirely portray the complexity of governance levels in the German context).

4.2. Description of policies

For this region, six policies were collected.

At the Danish national level, the policy of *Kulturarv* concerns the ‘protection of cultural heritage,’ ‘communication of cultural heritage,’ and ‘activation of cultural heritage’ in the entire Danish Kingdom (including Greenland and the Faroe Islands). The policies divide cultural heritage into Archives, Libraries, Historical monuments and dikes, Protections of Buildings (under Kulturarvsstyrelsen), Museums, Language, and Security related to the protection of said cultural heritage. As part of the laws, a section on repatriation was added in 2022.

In Germany, the state (Bundesland) policy *Kultur im Dialog: Kulturpolitische Leitlinien 2023* proposes development goals in the area of culture, broadly speaking, in Schleswig-Holstein until 2030. Specific areas in focus are “Cultural Infrastructure,” “Education,” “Cultural Heritage,” and “Digitalisation.” A central issue in the strategy is how to make the cultural institutions (archives, museums, monuments, etc.) ecologically sustainable in order to adapt to current climate challenges. The document also emphasizes the centrality of culture for social cohesion, including dialogue and community-building. Culture must be seen as a value for democratic processes. In the area of cultural heritage, there is an emphasis on ecological sustainability and cooperation with the tourism industry, as well as a more advanced digitalization of archives and libraries.

For each side, one municipality was selected as an example. For Denmark, the choice was to use Sønderborg kommune, whereas for Germany, the choice was to include the cultural policy of Stadt Flensburg.

Kulturkompasset Sønderborg 2025 aims at creating a ‘living culture’ and inspiring the citizens to ‘choose a different path.’ Culture is related to sustainability and regarded as a way to strengthen identity and social cohesion, as well as achieve a healthy and joyous life. It is also a way to bridge gaps between young and old, cultural differences, and social status. Four focus areas are chosen every four years, and every year, an action plan is developed by the municipality and implemented in each focus area. Every year, a cultural forum invites the citizens of Sønderborg to make suggestions for the upcoming action plan. The cultural forum also includes presentation stands where individual actors can promote their own work, and it is connected with an online forum where information can be found and new input made. The strategy is supposed to work as a

dynamic tool and through participatory processes. The strategy was developed as part of Sønderjylland-Schleswigs' bid to become the European cultural capital in 2017.

On the German side, cultural heritage policies in the context of municipalities are generally very limited, and this is also the case for Stadt Flensburg. The main objective of the “Flensburg 2030+” strategy concerns sustainability in a broad sense of the term and the strategy is not just aimed at the cultural heritage institutions. However, the document was chosen because it lacks anything more specific on cultural heritage. It seems as if actual policies are not in place in the area.

The emphasis in this 2030+ strategy for city development is thus on a diverse and worldly mindset of social and climate justice, all of which should make a good quality of life possible in the city. As the document states: “Flensburg übernimmt Verantwortung für eine sozial-ökologisch produktive, gemeinwohlorientierte, diverse und klimagerechte Stadt. Flensburg ist sozial gerecht und weltoffen, ermöglicht ein würdevolles und zufriedenes Leben und verpflichtet sich zu regionaler und globaler Gerechtigkeit. Gemeinsam gestalten wir den Wandel.“ Specific areas focused on are “Quality of life,” “Business development,” “Social integration,” “Climate adaptation and resilience,” “Infrastructure and mobility,” and “Cultural identity.” Cultural heritage plays a role in relation to specifically the last issue, cultural identity-formation (emphasis on the “active and integrating welcome and communication culture,” and the cross-border dimension is central in relation to culture and education).

The choices made about which level of policy-making to include in the analysis would have inferred that the Western parts of the border region are left out. This would also exclude a strong emphasis in these parts on the aspect of landscape heritage, as these parts are heavily influenced by how the Wadden Sea and thus vast areas in these parts have the status of UNESCO world heritage. We therefore chose to include one policy concerning the protection of the Wadden Sea to serve as an example of the distinction between the Eastern and Western parts of the region. The Leeuwarden Declaratiwas is signed by the Netherlands, Denmark, and Germany, with the goal to protect and manage the Wadden Sea as a single ecological entity shared by the three countries in accordance with the Guiding Principle, which is “to achieve, as far as possible, a natural and sustainable ecosystem in which natural processes proceed in an undisturbed way,” and applying the ecosystem approach,” with a recognition of the changed conditions caused by climate change and, hence, that “the overall goal of climate change adaptation in the Wadden Sea Area is to safeguard and promote the quality and integrity of the area as a natural and resilient ecosystem whilst ensuring the safety of its inhabitants and visitors.”

Finally, the cross-border agreement on cultural heritage promotion between municipalities, regions, and the states in Sønderjylland-Schleswig is also included to illustrate that regions and municipalities are working together in the field of culture. The agreement is mainly focused on art and movement, the creation of communities across borders, and citizens, in particular children and youth, participation in cultural activities. Language is also mentioned as an essential element of this. The common cultural heritage across the border is recognized as a means to achieve these goals. It thus has a very central role to play in relation to border crossing cultural community building. The talk is mainly about awareness creation among children and youth of the common historical heritage in order to make the younger generation understand the diverse and unifying cultural heritage of the region and how it intersects with their everyday lives, including the future prospects for this.

Several Interreg projects in the region could also have been included to exemplify this collaborative relation.

4.3. The cross-border dimension

The national-level policy documents contain a cross-border dimension: while the Danish document includes a reference to the Danish-German borderland in the Danish document, the German state-level document pays attention to a variety of international cooperation. At the local level, surprisingly, the strategy in Sønderborg focuses almost exclusively on Sønderborg as an isolated area and does not mention the cross-border dimension in any other way than as an asset to the cultural heritage in the area. It is Sønderborg, rather than the region as a whole, which has an international profile, and when the border region is mentioned as a common space for cultural experiences and as famous for its ability to collaborate across borders with culture as the most successful area, this is not integrated into the strategy itself as an asset. This is despite the strategy having developed out of a border-crossing bid to become the European cultural capital in 2017.

The minority cultures in the Danish-German borderland are mentioned under the living culture: The culture was nominated as UNESCO world heritage Under the label “The Danish-German minority-model – a framework for peaceful coexistence in a culturally diverse region.” According to the nomination, the model builds on respect for cultural diversity and the recognition of cultural diversity as a resource. The nomination was not successful.

. On the other hand, the German Flensburg document has a specific cross-border reference in relation to education, with the historical heritage of the city as a central part.

As for the remaining 2 special policies that were analyzed, both have cross-border dimensions. There is a clear acknowledgement that the Wadden Sea is a shared landscape and cultural heritage across borders, but the declaration is lacking description of more concrete cross-border collaboration at the local level.

Finally, the cross-border agreement on cultural heritage promotion between municipalities, regions, and the states in Sønderjylland-Schleswig specifically targets cross-border relations. It is clearly stipulated that the cultural heritage which is to be promoted is the heritage of the borderland, meaning the entire area of Sønderjylland and Schleswig (North and South Schleswig), not just one side of the border.

4.4. Alignment with EU policy and global agreements

The policies vary with regard to their alignment with EU policy and global agreements. At the Danish national level, the cultural heritage strategy does not mention the EU at all, whereas the UNESCO convention is a framework condition for the cultural heritage policies in the Danish context. Danmark has, in other words, ratified the 2005 Paris treaty, The Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions. This differs significantly from the German state-level document, in which jargon is heavily influenced by EU discourses, such as digitalization, participatory processes, and culture as the foundation of social cohesion but expressed in the unfolding of diversity and ecological sustainability. The document also mentions

the UNESCO cultural and natural heritage in the region, which is emphasized specifically in the strategy.

At the local level, the Sonderborg strategy reproduces some EU discourse, not the least because the strategy developed on the basis of the 2017 bid for European cultural capital, e.g., talks of sustainability and green transition, focus on the youth, relating cultural heritage and social cohesion; the many participatory elements in the strategy. But it is not concrete and international frameworks are not mentioned. The German Flensburg strategy heavily reproduces EU discourse, just like at the national level.

The Waddensee declaration relates to the UNESCO World Heritage Convention as the Wadden Sea is a UNESCO World Heritage (natural heritage). The International Maritime Organization (IMO) is also mentioned as an important liaison because of pollution stemming from the shipping industry. Thus, it is also aligned with EU policy since EU policy is aligned with the UNESCO declaration, which has been ratified by the EU member states.

5. Germany - France

5.1. Context

The French-German border region, for our purposes, consists of the Upper-Rhine region (Alsace on the French side and Baden on the German side) and the so-called “greater region” (encompassing in our study the French and German parts, i.e., Moselle on the French side and Saarland on the German side). Relevant policies in the French context were found at the regional level, although usually main legal and policy frameworks are given in Paris due to France being a very centralized state. Some local activities are organized from Strasbourg, the headquarters of the “Grand Est” region. Sometimes, the European Grouping of Territorial Cooperation (EGTC) is also involved. In the German context, the cultural heritage of the state Baden-Württemberg on the one hand, and of Saarland, on the other hand, provides the framework conditions for the lower governance levels, which are Kreis, Stadt, and Gemeinde (from now on referred to as municipalities even when this does not entirely portray the complexity of governance levels in the German context).

5.2. Description of policies

Three relevant policies were identified and analyzed. All three deal directly with cultural policy in the cross-border space.

The main objectives of the Grand Est's transborder cultural policy focus on creating a cross-border cultural space by strengthening cooperation with neighboring countries. It aims to enhance mutual cultural understanding, support cross-border projects, and develop international cultural collaborations. The policy addresses cultural heritage by promoting joint initiatives, such as professional exchanges and large-scale cultural events, ensuring that the region's rich cultural heritage is preserved and shared beyond borders. These actions foster a shared European cultural identity.

Le Forum Culture de la Conférence du Rhin supérieur (The Cultural Forum of the Upper Rhine Conference) has the main objectives of fostering cross-border cultural exchanges, supporting collaborative cultural projects, and enhancing the preservation and promotion of shared cultural heritage. By promoting mutual understanding and cooperation between regions, the policy aims to enrich cultural ties and encourage joint initiatives. It addresses cultural heritage by focusing on the sustainable management and valorization of significant cultural assets, ensuring their protection and celebration. Additionally, the policy supports cultural diversity and regional identity by facilitating diverse cultural expressions and activities, contributing to a vibrant and interconnected cultural landscape across national borders.

The Fonds culturel transfrontalier - Rhin supérieur is a cross-border agreement between France, Germany, and Switzerland that aims to promote cultural exchange and collaboration among France, Germany, and Switzerland by supporting cross-border projects that involve cultural organizations and artists from the Upper Rhine region. It focuses on enhancing and preserving the shared cultural heritage of the region through initiatives that document and celebrate its history and traditions. By funding joint cultural activities such as exhibitions and festivals, the policy

seeks to strengthen regional identity and foster mutual understanding across national borders. Key stakeholders include regional cultural institutions, local and regional authorities, cultural organizations, funding agencies, artists and cultural professionals, as well as the general public.

5.3. The cross-border dimension

All three documents are grounded in a cross-border context but not always on a local level. The Grand Est's transborder cultural policy focuses on fostering collaboration in general with neighboring countries, such as Germany, Belgium, and Luxembourg, to create a shared cultural space. The policy highlights cross-border cultural heritage attractions and encourages joint cultural initiatives across borders. Additionally, it has been applied in various cross-border contexts, such as joint cultural events and professional exchanges, reinforcing cultural ties and enhancing mutual understanding in the region.

The Cultural Forum of the Upper Rhine Conference policy explicitly mentions a cross-border regional dimension by focusing on enhancing cultural exchanges and collaborations between regions across national borders. It aims to support cultural projects and initiatives that span multiple countries, fostering cooperation and mutual enrichment between the participating regions. Specific cultural heritage attractions located on either side of the border are often highlighted and integrated into the policy's objectives to promote shared cultural experiences and conservation efforts. The policy has been relevant and applied in various cross-border contexts. It supports and facilitates joint cultural projects that involve multiple countries, showcasing its practical application in real-world cross-border scenarios. This includes collaborative cultural events, heritage conservation projects, and cross-border cultural exchanges that bring together stakeholders from different regions to work towards common cultural goals. The policy's relevance is evident in its efforts to address and manage cultural heritage and cultural activities that extend beyond national boundaries.

Finally, the transborder cultural agreement – Upper Rhine policy document specifically targets the Upper Rhine region, which spans parts of France, Germany, and Switzerland. It is designed to support cultural projects that involve collaboration between entities from these different countries. This cross-border approach is integral to the fund's purpose, fostering cultural exchange and joint initiatives that reflect the shared heritage and regional identity of the Upper Rhine area. The fund is used to support projects that operate across national borders, such as joint exhibitions, performances, and cultural festivals that involve partners from different countries in the Upper Rhine region. These projects illustrate the fund's practical application in a cross-border context, demonstrating its role in facilitating international cultural cooperation and preserving shared cultural heritage.

5.4. Alignment with EU policy and global agreements

The Grand Est's transborder cultural policy aligns with EU directives and broader European cultural policies. It emphasizes cross-border cooperation, artistic mobility, and cultural cohesion, which are key themes in EU frameworks like the European Agenda for Culture and Creative Europe. The use of language around cultural exchange, collaboration, and European identity also

reflects alignment with EU priorities for strengthening cultural ties and promoting shared heritage across member states. The policy aligns with international conventions, particularly UNESCO conventions on cultural diversity and heritage preservation. It promotes the safeguarding and sharing of cultural heritage through cross-border collaborations and aligns with global standards in heritage management. The focus on cultural diversity, cooperation, and international exchanges further reflects principles of global agreements aimed at protecting intangible and tangible cultural heritage.

The Cultural Forum of the Upper Rhine Conference policy is a European-focused strategy that does not mention international agreements but reflects the EU's support for cultural integration and regional cooperation, as outlined in the Creative Europe program and the European Agenda for Culture. These EU initiatives aim to foster cultural diversity, enhance cultural heritage, and support collaborative cultural activities across member states. Moreover, the policy's focus on the preservation and promotion of shared cultural heritage aligns with EU directives related to cultural heritage conservation, such as the European Heritage Label and the European Year of Cultural Heritage. The language used in the policy, such as references to sustainable management and the protection of cultural assets, is consistent with EU guidelines on heritage conservation and the promotion of cultural diversity.

Likewise, the transborder cultural agreement – Upper Rhine policy document is European by nature but refers to EU support initiatives for cultural cooperation and regional development and preservation of cultural heritage (e.g., Creative Europe).

6. Germany – Poland - Czechia

6.1. Context

The German-Polish-Czech trilateral border, the 500 km German-Polish border, and the 800 km Polish-Czech border together create a number of partially overlapping geographic, political, and cultural borderlands. To obtain the most representative picture, we decided to focus on the trilateral German-Polish-Czech Euroregion Neisse-Nysa-Nisa, the southern part of German-Polish border and the eastern part of the Polish-Czech borderlands, the Euroregion Těšín/Cieszyn Silesia. The focus in this area was on the regional and local levels, including cross-border institutional governance spaces. We also included a quick overview of since national (and the Free state of Saxony) policies, yet we deem them less important.

6.2. Description of policies

At the national level, the **National Strategy for Cultural Development** exists in Poland.

In Czechia, the **Regional Development Strategy of the Czech Republic 2021+**, created by the Ministry of Regional Development, is a key national document. It works with deprived/poor regions where also culture is less available. It also outlines concepts of culture and creative potential of metropolitan areas in connection to tourism. Generally, culture is seen as a part of regional development. Moreover, in regional centers and their surrounding rural areas, efforts are being made to preserve and promote folk and artistic crafts, which hold significant importance for the local economy in these regions. Cross-border cooperation is also mentioned, especially in connection to remote border areas.

Another notable document is the governmental **Strategic Framework Czech Republic 2030**. The culture of national minorities also deserves exceptional support. The state supports the development of knowledge of culture and the reduction of inequality in access to culture. Cultural policy must cooperate in an environment where the state and local government will be mutually beneficial to the private sector. It is a system setting of public tender principles. Self-government must be able to link state cultural policy with local conditions so that resources and attention are distributed in favor of quality cultural production at the local level.

The last document is the **State Cultural Policy 2021-2025**, prepared by the Ministry of Culture. It accentuates cultural heritage and supports (also financially) ethnic minorities' cultural activities.

The Free State of Saxony in Germany has developed several strategic documents to guide its cultural development. One of the key documents is the **Cultural Strategy of the Free State of Saxony until 2025**. This strategy outlines the state's objectives and measures for promoting and preserving cultural heritage, supporting contemporary arts, and ensuring broad access to cultural education and participation. The strategy emphasizes the importance of cultural diversity, innovation, and the integration of culture into various aspects of social and economic life.

Three regional-level documents were collected and analyzed.

The Czech Liberec region's development strategy focuses on six goals: prosperous, attractive, connected, caring, cooperating, and green regions. Cultural heritage is emphasized under the

"attractive region" goal, highlighting its societal importance. The strategy envisions preserving and promoting cultural heritage through the efforts of skilled professionals, civic initiatives, cultural institutions, and public-private partnerships. It aims to foster a positive connection between residents and the region's heritage while offering diverse cultural experiences that extend beyond regional borders. Key activities include preserving tangible and intangible heritage, improving historic buildings for accessibility and tourism, revitalizing monuments with modern facilities, and supporting cultural events. The strategy also emphasizes mapping and restoring minor and industrial heritage sites and promoting them through innovative and cross-border collaborations. Public education on historical monuments, traditional crafts, and intangible heritage is prioritized alongside programs to deepen knowledge of the region's cultural legacy. These efforts aim to enhance accessibility, engagement, and the sustainable use of cultural assets.

Another regional-level strategy is the ***Strategy of Development of the Polish Lower Silesia region***, which, as one of its five strategic aims, has "Responsible utilization of resources and the protection of the natural environment and cultural heritage." The policy document includes discussions and references to a number of heritage sites, historical monuments, cultural parks, and historic urban layouts. Regional heritage is seen as both natural and cultural, but the categorization between "natural" and "cultural" is rather intuitive and far from clear. Should we understand natural parks as products of nature or culture? What is the role of nature and culture in the functioning of spa cities?

As for German regions, only a fairly old document from 2009 could be identified as a relevant example, the **Signpost for Culture Development in Saxony** policy document. The policy aims to stabilize cultural heritage preservation and infrastructure, reinforce existing strengths, and initiate new cultural projects. It emphasizes safeguarding Saxony's cultural legacy while fostering innovation and development in the sector. Key stakeholders include cultural umbrella organizations (Kulturverbände), the Saxon Cultural Senate, the Saxon Academy of Arts, cultural policymakers, representatives of cultural institutions, individuals engaged in cultural work, and the Saxon State Ministry for Science and Art. Strategically, the policy calls for better coordination among funding bodies, regular evaluations, and multi-year funding commitments. Newly reformed cultural areas (Kulturräume) play a central role, supporting regionally significant organizations that incorporate regional traditions, educational roles, and tourism demands. Regular exchanges between these cultural areas, the Ministry, the Cultural Senate, and the Saxon Cultural Foundation (Kulturstiftung) are institutionalized to promote collaboration and knowledge sharing. These measures aim to create a sustainable and dynamic cultural landscape in Saxony.

Three city-level documents were collected and analyzed. The German municipal-level policy **"Cultural development planning 2020-2030 for the town Görlitz"** outlines a strategy for cultural development in Görlitz. Key focuses include cultural heritage, intercultural encounters, and cultural education. Notable projects include establishing a European Cultural Heritage Centre centered on 17th-century theologian Jakob Böhme, doubling the audience of the Görlitzer Collections, expanding the Upper Lusatian Library of the Sciences, and digitizing local archives. Cross-border cooperation with Zgorzelec includes reconstructing the city park and Neisse river shores. Efforts will also preserve Silesian art and traditions, with events like the Silesian Music Festival fostering cultural continuity across the Neisse. Cultural education seeks to integrate art and culture into early education and societal institutions. Collaboration between cultural and educational organizations will provide inclusive opportunities for intercultural exchange. Görlitz-Zgorzelec aims to become a "laboratory of understanding," fostering European integration. The Polish Development Strategy of the city Zgorzelec for the years 2015-2025 aims at making the city

a city that, among other things, skilfully uses the advantage of its location at the meeting point of three borders, cooperation with its neighbors, a special role of culture in the process of social change, and an ordered and revitalized spatial structure. Several strategic objectives relate to culture and cultural heritage in various ways, such as to have active residents and a well-developed cultural offer. In the western part of the researched Czech border, there is no divided city, such as Görlitz-Zgorzelec or Český Těšín-Cieszyn. However, Hrádek nad Nisou is an interesting municipality bordering the German town of Zittau and the Polish town of Bogatynia. In **Hrádek nad Nisou's Development Program for period from 2017 (updated in 2023)**, there are mentions of culture and cross-border dimensions. According to the plan, cross-border ties are mainly based on European projects, inbound one-day tourism and cheaper services in the city, especially for German visitors. A persistent problem is the absence or minimum of spontaneous ones of cross-border ties. The border is still perceived as a barrier. The cultural section is mostly unilateral and focuses on library, information center, cultural house or gallery activities. The basic subject in the field of culture is in the city in beneficial society Gate of the Three-border Region. This company was founded in 2010, and its mission is to organize and provide cultural and social events and support for tourism in the city. Its cross-border spirit is not only in its name. For example, it takes part in organizing an annual international festival, the Three-border Region Celebration. It takes place alternately in the Czech Republic, Poland and Germany.

Five documents produced by institutionalized cross-border cooperation were collected and analyzed.

The **Action and Development Plan of the Spree-Neisse-Bóbr Euroregion for 2021-2027**, with a perspective until 2030, contains practical guidelines that are the basis for the Euroregion's cross-border activities in the programming period 2021-2027. **Relevant strategies refer to cohesion and quality of life.** The document emphasizes that the key to a common understanding is to know the language and culture of one's neighbour. Accordingly, the partners in the Euroregion will focus on ensuring that every child and young person has ongoing opportunities to learn the neighbouring language. It will also be important for them to provide specialized language learning at adult education institutions in the Euroregion. The presence in the region of historic parks, the cross-border UNESCO Geopark Muskau Arc, the strong influence of open-cast mining, cities offering cultural experiences, and well-preserved historic urban complexes are stated to be important for the quality of life.

The **Transnational cooperation for sustainable development within the EGTC Muskau Bend** concerns the coordination, facilitation, and promotion of German-Polish cross-border cooperation within the area of Muskau Bend Geopark. According to paragraph 4 of the Convention, one of the main tasks of the EGTC is to cooperate in the protection of the geological and cultural heritage, the conservation of the landscape, and animate nature. The convention and statutes were signed by a total of 14 local authorities on both the local (cities, municipalities, districts) and regional (German Länder and Polish voivodeships) levels. In order to implement the stated strategic objectives, EGTC was set up as a limited liability partnership with a Polish chairman and his two German deputies.

The **Strategy of the Neisse-Nisa-Nysa Euroregion 2021-2027** is a strategy for developing cross-border cooperation in areas where it has the greatest benefits. The strategy defines cooperation priorities for a period consistent with the European Union's programming period. It also aims to target future funding for small projects managed by the Neisse-Nisa-Nysa Euroregion. The

specific objectives include highlighting the cultural heritage of the Euroregion for society, creating a common identity, preserving the historical landscape and its presentation, deepening cooperation in the field of culture, and developing cooperation between educational and training institutions, the transfer of knowledge and understanding of common history, and the creation of a common identity.

The Development strategy of the Cieszyn Silesia Euroregion for 2021-2027 is a response to the processes currently taking place in the world and on the Polish-Czech border, resulting from many factors, including the COVID-19 pandemic, and consistent with policy objectives of the new European Union cohesion policy. The vision of the strategy includes, among others, references to a strong cultural identity and a sense of belonging to a region where ethnicity, common roots, and regional creativity are nurtured, as well as to create a unique, individual image of individual towns based on modern technologies and cultural values. In turn, the strategy's mission refers, among other things, to care for the natural and cultural heritage.

A bilateral policy document is the **Polish-German Cross-Border Tourism Development Concept in the Gubin-Guben Eurocity**. The document defines — based on an analysis of the existing situation—areas, and forms of tourism development for both cities, ways of linking existing offers of the Polish and German sides, and new cross-border development directions. Objectives include the creation of a cross-border tourist functional area in the city of Guben on the German side and the Union of Gubin Municipalities on the Polish side and the creation of a European grouping of territorial cooperation to manage tourism development in the cross-border tourist functional area.

Another bilateral urban policy document is the **Cross-border cooperation strategy of Cieszyn and Český Těšín in the context of the development of the Cieszyn Silesia Euroregion**, which aims at creating a functional space for social coexistence, cultural life, and better mutual acquaintance between the communities of Cieszyn and Český Těšín based on the cross-border cooperation platform of both local governments and the Cieszyn Silesia Euroregion. Relevant operational objectives for this study include a common information policy (aimed at increasing the interest of local media), a coherent cross-border tourist offer, and a cross-border cultural and sports policy.

6.3. The cross-border dimension

The 3 regional policy documents contain cross-border dimensions. However, how that is done differs. In the Czech Liberec regional plan, references are mainly to the possibility of financing some activities from INTERREG projects. Other mentions of cross-border issues refer to the economic potential of nearby cities (Zittau) or the possibility of attracting visitors from Germany and Poland. In the Polish Lower Silesia document, borders are characterized as “running along natural barriers” – rivers (Nysa Łużycka river) and mountains (Sudety mountains). Capitals of neighboring countries – Berlin in Germany and Prague in Czechia – are mentioned as lying closely to the voivodeship, and the ties to different European cities are seen as beneficial to the development. In the section on “Transport,” the Czech-Polish and German-Polish borderlands are mentioned as contributing factors to the potential of cycling (together with varied terrain with a

predominance of lowland areas, dense settlement network strongly connected to the railway network, as well as its advantages of natural, landscape and cultural character). In the section on “Strategic analysis of territorial dimension of politics of development,” the word “borderland region” is mentioned as one of many functional regions inscribed in the project of the spatial development plan of the voivodeship. The mountainous/borderland region was presented on the map. In the section on “Potentials and barriers of development of sub-regions,” the role of the borderland for different subregions is recognized. Border crossings and their restrictions in the transport of high-tonnage goods are mentioned as weaknesses/dangers of the transport system and communication in a SWAT analysis. In a table with strategic aims, operational aims, and strategic projects, the last operational aim is called “Supporting interregional and cross-border cooperation.” It is mentioned as part of the “Strengthening of spatial cohesion of the region.” Further on in the document, three functional regions are seen as ascribed to the operational aim of “Supporting interregional and cross-border cooperation”: jeleniogórski, wałbrzyski, and mountainous/borderland. In the German Saxony regional plan, the document mentions the continuation and deepening of cross-border cultural care and cultural exchanges with central and eastern European states. However, only one example is mentioned, namely the Polish-German Fürst-Pückler-Park/Park Mużakowski in Muskau and Łęknica, a joint UNESCO World Heritage Site. Further, cooperation and further common cultural projects across Saxony’s borders (within Germany and beyond) are envisioned in the area of historical exhibitions and musical culture.

The 2 city-level documents both contain some references to cross-border issues. The Górlitz policy mentions the partner town Zgorzelec across the river Neisse under several initiatives, or Interreg projects, as well as initiatives emanating from the Górlitz town council. Zgorzelec’s own plans are not taken into consideration. In a similar vein, the Zgorzelec plan contains a general reference to cooperation with the German city of Górlitz, which resulted in the creation of the European City of Górlitz/Zgorzelec. The document also mentions that the city's location on the border with Germany and close to the Czech Republic is crucial for its development. Zgorzelec was the main initiator of the creation of the Neisse-Nysa-Nissa Euroregion. Significant tourist and cultural potential in the immediate vicinity of Zgorzelec, particularly concentrated in the city of Górlitz, is cited as an opportunity for development. However, the dominant role of Górlitz in the European City of Zgorzelec - Górlitz is perceived as a threat.

The policy documents produced by cross-border cooperation institutions were formulated as tools for cross-border cooperation and thus naturally have a cross-border dimension.

6.4. Alignment with EU policies

The Czech and Polish regional policy documents mention EU funds as vital for the implementation of financial strategy. The reform of the Cohesion Policy and Common Agricultural Policy is recognized as the source of financial insecurity. In the German Saxony policy document, Europe is mentioned several times, but more in an ideational sense rather than by reference to the EU or to specific EU directives or policies. Other international references are mostly missing, but the Saxony policy explicitly references the UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage, the UNESCO Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions, the Washington Principles on Nazi-Confiscated Art, and the Terezin Declaration of 2009.

The municipal documents do not explicitly refer to EU documents, except for mentioning Interreg or European funds. The UNESCO World Heritage policy is hinted at when Görlitz's bid for World Heritage site status is mentioned. The Zgorzelec does not refer to international dimensions but to national programs of natural preservation.

The cross-border cooperation institutions mostly have some form of European alignment. For instance,

The Development strategy of the Cieszyn Silesia Euroregion for 2021-2027 fits into the thematic objectives of the new cohesion policy of the European Union: a more competitive and smarter Europe, a greener, low carbon transitioning towards a net zero carbon economy, a more connected Europe by enhancing mobility; a more social and inclusive Europe; Europe closer to citizens by fostering the sustainable and integrated development of all types of territories. Cultural heritage is directly linked with more social and inclusive European objectives.

The **Transnational cooperation for the sustainable development within the EGTC Muskau Bend document** refers to the European Union only in the context of its laws (regulations), which provide for the establishment of such supranational companies and regulate specific issues. Only Article 4 of the Convention mentions that the company's activities are intended to contribute to the strengthening of the economic, social, and territorial cohesion of the European Union. Thus, these provisions, together with the additional tasks envisaged in the documents (such as cooperation on the protection of the geological and cultural heritage, the protection of landscapes and living nature) are in line with the EU's objectives and values as provided for in Article 3 of the Lisbon Treaty. The language used on this issue is also consistent, although it should be borne in mind that this is only a small part of both documents.

The Strategy of the Neisse-Nisa-Nysa Euroregion 2021-2027 defines cooperation priorities for a period consistent with the programming period of the European Union. The Euroregion is involved in the development of future programmes and can, therefore, contribute to its area in both the analytical and conceptual parts of future programmes. The document also aims to guide future small project funds managed by the Euroregion. // Yes. Although there are no direct references in the text of the strategy to international conventions or agreements on the protection or management of cultural heritage, the document is in line with the regional cooperation agreement under the name "Euroregion Neisse-Nisa-Nisa." This compatibility relates, among other things, to the cultural objectives of the Euroregion – the improvement of cultural living conditions, cultural exchange, and the care of the common cultural heritage.

The Lower Silesia strategy is in line with the regional cooperation agreement under the name "Cieszyn Silesia Euroregion" signed between Stowarzyszenie Rozwoju i Współpracy Regionalnej „Olza” (the "Olza" Association for Development and Regional Cooperation) and Regionální sdružení územní spolupráce Těšínského Slezska (Regional Association for Territorial Cooperation of Cieszyn Silesia). This compatibility concerns, among other things, the cultural objectives of the Euroregion – cultural exchange and care of the common cultural heritage as well as actions supporting the development of culture, especially the exchange of information in this field.

The Gubin-Guben policy concept refers to the principle of coordination related to combining activities, mechanisms, and instruments of EU cohesion policy, the principle of subsidiarity, the principle of concentration, and the principle of partnership. The document also refers to the European Grouping of Territorial Cooperation as the most advanced form of institutional and legal cross-border cooperation in the European Union, which can be used to manage tourism development in the Eurocity. Notably, the document is consistent with the agreement on the

establishment of the Spree-Neisse-Bóbr Euroregion. This compatibility is due to the document's synergy with the Euroregion's cultural objectives.

The development strategy of the Cieszyn Silesia Euroregion refers to the objectives and directions of EU policy on the conditions and forms of territorial cooperation in the 2020+ perspective. In addition, the document envisages as the last of the main stages of its implementation the concept of creating a Eurocity Cieszyn-Český Těšín 2025, based on the European Grouping of Territorial Cooperation (EGTC). EGTC regulations are contained in Regulation (EC) No. 1082/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006. Although there are no direct references in the text of the strategy to international conventions or agreements on the protection or management of cultural heritage, the document is in line with the regional cooperation agreement under the name "Cieszyn Silesia Euroregion." This compatibility is due both to the synergy of the strategy with the Euroregion's cultural objectives and to the links and co-responsibility of the entities that implement it. In addition to the self-governments of Cieszyn and Český Těšín, the document is also implemented by the Polish and Czech sides of the aforementioned agreement – Stowarzyszenie Rozwoju i Współpracy Regionalnej „Olza” (the "Olza" Association for Development and Regional Cooperation) and Regionální sdružení územní spolupráce Těšínského Slezska (Regional Association for Territorial Cooperation of Cieszyn Silesia).

7. Hungary - Slovakia

7.1. Context

The border between Hungary and Slovakia is 679 kilometers long and formed by waterways (the Danube and Ipoly/Ipel' rivers) or mountains (the Carpathians). In the language of the European Union's program for cross-border cooperation support, five NUTS3 level counties on the Slovak side and eight on the Hungarian constitute one single border area. Both countries are relatively centralized, combining a strong state with a large number of municipalities (fragmentation) and relatively weak regional structures. This area covers 61,500 square kilometers, has a population of almost 9 million, and includes the capitals of both countries. While such a definition of what a border area is can be useful, it is clear that it does include territory that is not considered to be close to a border in everyday thinking. For instance, while Bratislava defines itself as a border city ("the only capital to border two neighboring countries"), Budapest tends to emphasize its core/center character ("lies in the heart of the Carpathian Basin").³¹ The border region that is researched in B-shapes project comprises the Slovak Region of Nitra (with focus on border town with substantial Hungarian minority, Štúrovo and Esztergom) and the Hungarian County of Komárom-Esztergom. It is important to note that there is a significant Hungarian-speaking minority on the Slovak side of this border, originating with the rebordering processes after World War I.

7.2. Description of policies

Komárom-Esztergom does not seem to have produced any publicly available policy document specifically devoted to cultural heritage, but the field is covered in the County's more general spatial development documents. In Hungary, each county is obliged to compile or revise the earlier version of its Integrated Territorial Program (ITP), which sets out the guidelines and requires the approval of the relevant ministry. Based on that concept paper, two further documents are produced: the Strategic Program (SP) defines the goals and priorities, while the Operative Program (OP) describes how they should be achieved. All three documents should cover a period of seven years due to their alignment with the EU's budget cycles. The spatial development programs cover many fields – including cultural heritage, though often under the more overarching theme of tourism development. They want to strengthen heritage management, especially in Esztergom. The concept is 'to continue doing integrated heritage management, building on cultural and natural values.' One of the priorities is developing tourism, under which one specific goal is to maintain 'the thematic international collaborations and networks such as the [Danube Limes](#), the [Street of Emperors and Kings](#), the [European Route of Industrial Heritage](#), [SacraVelo](#), etc.' Additionally, some county-level heritage sites shall also be developed, including those related to the Eszterházy family, castles, industrial/mining heritage, as well as a visitor centre for an archaeological exhibition. In addition to EU funds, they want to use national sources such as the National Chateaux and Castle Program. They also count on enterprises to cooperate with tourism actors around heritage sites and urge thematic cooperations around similar types of heritage like castle tourism or pilgrimage tourism.

On the Slovak side, the Strategy of Development of the Nitra Region has as its main goals six priorities: Competitive and knowledge-based economy; Quality and clean environment; Effective infrastructure and sustainable mobility; Social development of the region and the support of communities; Quality and inclusive education; Smart regional development with an emphasis on participation and cooperation. Regarding the care of cultural heritage, it is included under the priority social development of the region and the support of communities (under the goal of Development of culture and sport and the subgoal of Sustainable restoration, preservation, and use of cultural heritage). The strategy mentions that "the development of tourism must be based on the completion of a comprehensive offer and the missing integrated products ensuring better use of natural and cultural heritage together with the completion of key infrastructure, while it is necessary to intensify ties and the level of cooperation between regional actors, to support the use of digital and SMART solutions together with the systematic promotion of destinations on the territory of the Nitra Region." The term cultural heritage is mentioned in the document several times, e.g., in a SWOT analysis. The strategy includes activities comprising: (1) Preservation of cultural heritage and the development of cultural infrastructure and tourism in the territory of the region, primarily through the restoration and revitalization of cultural monuments; (2) Their multifunctional use for tourism, cultural and creative industries, interactive presentation of cultural heritage, education, and training in this area. (3) Better accessibility and serviceability of regional touristic destinations – cultural and natural assets. (4) Better marketing presentation and promotion.

The strategic development documents of two selected municipalities with a substantial Hungarian minority located immediately on the border river Dabube (Štúrovo and Komárno) are

fragment formalistic documents, which seem to limit their plan in the cultural field to the reconstructions of cinemas and places used for cultural gatherings.

The third analysed policy is the Law resulting in the establishment of a commissioned foundation operating the Central European Built Heritage Protection Foundation (KEÉÖMA). This is a policy that is aimed at the Hungarian state's purchasing and maintaining of built cultural heritage in neighbouring countries, including Slovakia. More specifically, setting up KEÉÖMA was motivated in the 2020 law by the desire 'to promote activities aimed at the maintenance and protection of buildings and constructions in Central Europe, currently protected or unprotected but carrying cultural, historical, aesthetic or architectural value and significance for Hungarian historical and cultural heritage, aesthetic roots, past, and traditions.'

7.3. The cross-border dimension

The three analysed documents demonstrate strong cross-border thinking. The Hungarian regional document explicitly describes the southwestern Slovakian regions as having an accentuated role: due to the investments into transport infrastructure realised during the previous as well as current budget periods, 'the dividing role of the Danube has been ever more reduced, and there is significant development potential in the growth of the intensity of contacts' including on the labor market, especially around the cities Komárom and Esztergom. This role is further strengthened by the operations of the EGTCs. The document emphasizes organic linkages, such as 'Esztergom having almost grown together with Štúrovo' (ITP, p. 32). As the SP (p. 41) sets out, the Slovak-Hungarian borderland shall be seen as one target area for tourism, envisioned as a shared [Danubeland](#). Further, the County's bike-path network shall be 'linked with Slovakia's existing and planned infrastructure' (SP, p. 51). In realising these investments, the [HU-SK Partnership Program](#) plays an important role, largely funded by the ERDF (OP, p. 12). A cross-border clearway (OP, p. 18) and a concomitant new road and railway bridge (OP, pp 19, 20) are also planned. Another cross-border dimension goes beyond the immediate borderland and pertains to macroregional heritage projects and European transport corridors. Likewise, in the Nitra Strategy of Development and [local strategies of Štúrovo and Komárno](#), the cross-border dimension or cooperation is mentioned several times, even if perhaps somewhat weaker than on the Hungarian side. The referrals include the possibility of financing some activities from the European INTERREG program. Institutionalized cooperation in the form of Euroregions or EGTCs is mentioned but without concrete plans or policies.

Finally, the whole undertaking described in KEÉÖMA is about cross-border built cultural heritage purchasing and management (though not just in the immediate borderland).

7.4. Alignment with EU policies

The goals of the Hungarian regional policies are explicitly aligned with the EU sectoral goals PO1–PO5, which are also described in the SP (p. 11) and mentioned in the OP (p. 11). Further, it is also mentioned in each of the five priorities set out in both the SP and OP with which EU sectoral goals

the respective priority is aligned. The links with European transport corridors are mentioned as well (SP, p. 47). Also invoked is the Partnership Agreement between the EU and Hungary, which locates 'how EU sources arriving in Hungary will support national and EU sectoral goals' (SP, p. 63). It is also pinned down in the OP (p. 8) which EU Funds will be relied on in addition to national sources (OP, pp 9, 14–15) and also which EU programs (OP, p. 13). On the other hand, international conventions or agreements are not explicitly referred to. World heritage sites or ones that may be recognized as such are mentioned, but these are not put in the context of international cooperation or agreements. The Slovak regional policy only refers to EU funds. Most likely, the strategy is aligned with EU and internationally agreed goals, but the strategy lacks references to any international documents. Given that the text of the strategy is very general and its objectives are in line with the Slovak and the pan-European concept of cultural heritage protection, it is to be expected that it is aligned. In terms of city strategies, the Komárno city strategy plans the further development of its European Courtyard, the unique square celebrating European integration. The essence of its architectural design lies in the fact that the individual buildings of the square present, in a stylized form, architectural features characteristic of the construction styles of a wide range of European countries and regions.

As for the Central European Built Heritage Protection Foundation (KEÉÖMA), the EU has neither been mentioned in the law nor in media articles accessed. However, purchasing built cultural heritage – just as basically anything – hardly runs against any EU policy (with the free movement of capital constituting one of the most fundamental pillars of the Union). In the described endeavours of the Hungarian govt, the term 'Europe' only features to the extent that the name of the Foundation includes the label 'Central European' (which in current Hungarian political discourse often refers to Hungary and its neighbourhood).

8. Austria – Italy

8.1. Context

The Autonomous Province of Bolzano/Bozen, also known as South Tyrol, is located in northern Italy, on the Austrian and Swiss borders. Its population of approximately 516,000 is composed of 70% German speakers, 26% Italian speakers, 4.5% Latin speakers, and a growing number of migrants. The large percentage of German speakers is the result of a redrawing of borders after the First World War, when South Tyrol, until then part of the Habsburg Empire, became part of Italy. After significant social and political tensions, in 1972, South Tyrol received the Second Statute of Autonomy, a complex power-sharing system through which the German-speaking population in South Tyrol enjoys one of the world's most advanced systems of minority protection. Socio-cultural, political, and economic ties between the German-speaking minority in South Tyrol and the Austrian Land Tyrol are strong, and together with the Trentino, South Tyrol, and Tyrol, form an integrated border area through the cross-border region "Euregio Tyrol-South Tyrol-Trentino." Austria is a federal state, and Italy is a unitary state with a number of regions with special autonomies, meaning that relevant policies could be found at the national, federal/regional, and local levels.

8.2. Description of policies

Six documents were analysed, two of which were at a national level, one regional, one local, and two produced by the Euroregion Tyrol-South Tyrol-Trentino.

The Federal Guidelines for Cultural Policies of the Austrian Ministry of Culture are the current cultural policy of Austria, indicating its basic framework, and outlining its future strategic development through 8 macro areas. The policy addresses cultural heritage by committing to the preservation of Austria's cultural heritage while adapting cultural infrastructure to contemporary needs, including accessibility and sustainability; by highlighting the importance of digitalizing cultural heritage; and by ensuring adequate funding for the preservation and promotion of cultural heritage. It explicitly highlights the need to adequately deal with heritage objects that were seized during Nazi times and of (post-)colonial provenance.

On the Italian side, a somewhat different policy document was identified: the National Plan for the Digitalisation of Cultural Heritage 2022-2023, which constitutes the strategic vision with which the Italian Ministry of Culture, in agreement with the Regions, intends to promote and organize the process of digital transformation in the five-year period 2022-2026 in the cultural. It also constitutes the strategic, intellectual, and technical reference framework for the realization of the objectives of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRP). The concept of cultural heritage is expanded to include digital heritage, recognizing both digitally born and digitized resources as integral parts of the cultural ecosystem. Among other things, the plan envisions the establishment of a technological infrastructure to support the digitalization of cultural assets, products, services, and processes and ensure the alignment with the broader European digital and green transition strategies.

The policy for the Pustertal region in South Tyrol, Italy, focuses on sustainable development with four main objectives: creating an attractive and sustainable living environment, enhancing regional identity through cultural and natural diversity, promoting future-oriented economic growth, and ensuring environmental and climate protection. It addresses cultural heritage by emphasizing the preservation of cultural diversity and regional identity, supporting projects that safeguard historical sites, traditional crafts, and local customs to maintain the region's cultural richness. Additionally, it promotes multilingualism and cultural initiatives by encouraging the preservation and support of the Ladin language and culture alongside German and Italian, recognizing the multilingual character of the region as integral to its heritage.

The key objective of the Charter of the Museums of the Euroregion Tyrol-South Tyrol-Trentino for sustainable development is to create a cross-border euro-regional framework for museums to contribute to the sustainable development of territories and their societies. By documenting and preserving the tangible and intangible cultural heritage, museums commit to actively involve communities and visitors in the new interpretation of contemporary society and its evolution. The charter also promotes the protection of cultural heritage and the preservation of the environment based on the criteria of the cultural landscape, which is understood as a set of cultural and historical biodiversity that is worthy of preservation and central to social cohesion and well-being. Finally, it highlights the importance of promoting inclusivity and accessibility of all to cultural heritage, including marginalised groups.

The policy concerning the "Euregio-Museumsjahr 2021⁹" seeks to enhance cross-border cultural cooperation across the regions of Tyrol (Austria), South Tyrol (Italy), and Trentino (Italy). It provides funding for small museums to ensure that lesser-known cultural heritage sites and collections receive attention and resources. The key stakeholders involved in the development and implementation of the policy are the political and administrative cross-border institutions within the EGTC Tyrol-South Tyrol-Trentino, and there is a steering group which is composed of representatives from the museums of the member regions, representatives from the respective provincial public departments and representatives from the EGTC General Secretariat.

The main objectives of the "Handbuch Kulturgüterschutz" (HB-KGS) are to ensure the protection and preservation of movable cultural assets during emergencies such as fire, natural disasters, and floods. The policy provides practical guidelines for institutions and individuals responsible for cultural heritage to effectively plan and execute emergency measures. The policy defines cultural heritage by drawing on the COE and UNESCO definitions. It also addresses cultural heritage by underscoring its cultural, historical, and identity value and the need to protect it as part of humanity's shared heritage.

⁹ In 2025, the next cross-border Euregio museum year will take place. The thematic focus is "1525-2025 Museum. keep thinking!". It is based on the memory of the historical figure Michael Gaismair and the Peasants' Wars in this region in 1525. The Euregio Museum Year 2025 is using this event, which shaped the history of the three countries, as an opportunity to address questions of social justice, dealing with crises and social upheavals, and resistance in a museum context.

8.3. The cross-border dimension

None of the two national documents have a cross-border dimension, although the Federal Guidelines for Cultural Policies of the Austrian Ministry of Culture emphasize international cooperation in general. Likewise, the Italian Handbook for the protection of cultural assets lacks references to border regions and borderlands. The local example of the Pustertal policy, on the other hand, does include a cross-border dimension, which is evident in its alignment with cross-border cooperation programs and its emphasis on regional collaboration beyond national borders. The policy explicitly refers to the Interreg program. It also emphasizes the preservation and promotion of cultural heritage that is shared across borders. This includes efforts to preserve and promote languages, traditions, and historical sites that are significant to both sides of the border. The policy also supports cross-border economic activities, particularly in sectors like tourism, agriculture, and crafts, which are vital to the regional economies on both sides of the border. There is a focus on improving cross-border infrastructure, particularly transportation networks, to enhance mobility and connectivity between the regions. Finally, it supports initiatives that promote multilingualism and cultural exchange between the communities on both sides of the border. This is particularly important in the Pustertal region, where multiple languages and cultural identities coexist.

The two documents produced by the Euroregion naturally have a significant cross-border dimension. The Charter of the Museums explicitly promotes cross-border cultural coordination, cooperation, and exchange, advocating for the sharing of resources, knowledge, and best practices among the museums in the Euregio. By focusing on the collective heritage and identity of the Euregio, the policy strengthens a shared sense of belonging among Tyrol, South Tyrol, and Trentino. By fostering community engagement and inclusivity, the policy aims to create a unified cultural space that transcends state boundaries. For the policy of the Museum year, the cross-border dimension is integral to its objectives and implementation strategies. The policy aims to foster cultural cooperation and integration across the regions of Tyrol in Austria and South Tyrol and Trentino in Italy. This comes through as governance set-up, shared cultural themes (in 2021 transport, transit, and mobility), collaborative projects, joint funding approaches, and a coordinated market strategy for public engagement and outreach.

8.4. Alignment with EU policies

Both national documents refer to EU and global policies:

The Austrian federal guidelines refer several times to the NextGenerationEU recovery fund and mention the integration of EU funds for supporting ecological investments in cultural institutions. The document is aligned with several UNESCO and COE conventions, such as the Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, the Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage, or the Framework Convention on the Value of Cultural Heritage for Society. It also refers to the Washington Principles on Nazi-Confiscated Art. The Italian National Plan for the Digitalisation of Cultural Heritage 2022-2023 explicitly references the Council conclusions of 21 May 2014 on cultural heritage as a strategic resource for a sustainable Europe, the EU Commission's recommendations on the creation of a European data space for cultural heritage (2021/1970), the European Green Deal and Next Generation EU. It also aligns with the EU Directive 2019/1024 on open data and the reuse of public sector information. It also refers to the Horizon Europe programme. The document also explicitly refers to the CoE

Faro Convention and the Europa Nostra Cultural Heritage Green Paper. Although not explicitly named, the document also aligns with the principles outlined in various UNESCO conventions, such as the Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage and the Convention concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage.

Likewise, the local Pustertal policy mentions not less than 10 European policies and institutions, including general ones such as the European Regional Development Fund, the LEADER program, the Digital Europe program, and culturally related ones such as the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, particularly with respect to the protection of cultural heritage and linguistic rights, and also environmental strategies such as EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and EU Habitats Directive. Furthermore, the document cites the UNESCO Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage (1972), Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage (2003), Faro Convention, 2005; European Landscape Convention (2000); International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR, 1966).

The 2 euroregional documents, on the other hand, do not specifically cite EU policies or institutions but incorporate goals and objectives that resonate with broader EU policies and initiatives related to cultural heritage, sustainable development, and inclusivity (European Framework for Action on Cultural Heritage; EU Agenda for Culture; EU Strategy for Sustainable Development; European Green Deal; Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025; EU Cohesion Policy.) Related to global cultural governance, the charter refers to the SDGs, the UNESCO Culture 2030 Indicators, the ICOM-OECD 2018 Guide for Local Governments and Museums, and the UNESCO Indicators for Environmental and Resilience, whereas the Museum year document only does this implicitly.

9. Bulgaria – Greece - Turkey

9.1. Context

The border region between Greece, Bulgaria, and Turkey, for our purposes, encompasses the areas of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace in Greece, Southern Bulgaria (notably regions close to Plovdiv and the Rhodope Mountains), and Eastern Thrace in Turkey. Relevant policies in the Greek context are primarily found at the national level but also include regional programs supported by European initiatives like INTERREG, which promotes cross-border cooperation. Bulgaria's policies on cultural heritage preservation and economic development are influenced by national priorities but often incorporate EU directives, particularly for regional development along the Greek-Bulgarian border. In Turkey, heritage preservation efforts in Eastern Thrace focus on safeguarding cultural sites and managing risks related to natural disasters, with a significant role played by local governance bodies alongside national guidelines. Cross-border cooperation is facilitated by EU programs and agreements, which aim to strengthen cultural, social, and economic ties across these regions, highlighting shared heritage and collaborative development.

9.2. Description of policies

For the regions of Greece, Bulgaria, and Turkey, nine policies were collected. These policies demonstrate a wide-ranging commitment to cultural heritage preservation, regional cooperation, and adaptation to environmental challenges, reflecting each country's unique historical and environmental context.

At the national level in Greece, the policy *Κλιματική Αλλαγή και Πολιτιστική Κληρονομιά* (Climate Change and Cultural Heritage) addresses the impact of climate change on cultural assets. Administered by the Ministry of Culture and Sports, this policy focuses on safeguarding tangible and intangible cultural heritage from climate risks such as extreme weather events and sea-level rise. The policy framework is structured around diagnostics, monitoring, prevention, and conservation. Cross-border elements are reflected in partnerships with international bodies, including UNESCO and ICOMOS, with a particular emphasis on collaboration for climate adaptation.

Greece also participates in the *Πολιτιστική Κληρονομιά και Βιωσιμότητα: Πρακτικός Οδηγός* (Cultural Heritage and Sustainability: Practical Guide), part of the INTERREG Europe initiative. This regional policy emphasizes sustainability in cultural heritage through cross-border cooperation and self-sustaining funding models. Engaging local communities and public-private partnerships are key elements aiming to build long-term resilience in the cultural sector across multiple European nations, including Greece, Poland, and Italy.

Locally, the city of Thessaloniki has implemented *Ανθεκτικότητα και πολιτιστική κληρονομιά των πόλεων* (Resilience and Cultural Heritage of Cities), which integrates cultural preservation with urban resilience strategies. In collaboration with Aristotle University, this municipal strategy places cultural heritage within the broader scope of urban planning. It emphasizes community involvement and education to reinforce Thessaloniki's historical identity amidst urban development pressures.

The *Ετήσιο Σχέδιο Δράσης 2024* (Annual Action Plan 2024) represents a comprehensive national strategy for cultural heritage in Greece, focusing on preservation, accessibility, and sustainability. It includes targeted interventions to restore key heritage sites, modernise museums, and improve infrastructure, with an emphasis on supporting vulnerable groups and addressing climate resilience. This policy also fosters international collaborations, leveraging partnerships with UNESCO and other organisations to promote Greece as a cultural hub in the Mediterranean and EU regions.

In Bulgaria, the *National Cultural Policy Regarding the Relationship "Culture – Development"* positions culture as a catalyst for economic growth and social cohesion. Issued by Bulgaria's Ministry of Culture, this policy promotes the cultural and creative industries, with a focus on both tangible and intangible heritage. The policy aligns with EU cultural strategies, aiming to integrate cultural heritage within the national economy, strengthen community identity, and foster cross-border collaborations with neighboring regions.

Additionally, Bulgaria's *Strategy for the Development of Bulgarian Culture 2019-2029* outlines strategic goals for cultural preservation and creative industry growth. It encourages the use of digital platforms for cultural content, supporting accessibility and promoting cultural tourism. Cross-border cultural initiatives are central to this strategy, which includes collaborative projects in heritage preservation, especially with other EU countries.

Turkey's approach to cultural heritage preservation is exemplified by the policy *Kültürel Mirasın Korunmasında Yerel Yönetimlerin Rolü* (The Role of Local Governments in Protecting Cultural Heritage), which emphasizes local governance in heritage preservation. Coordinated by UCLG-MEWA, this policy involves local municipalities, universities, and community organizations in heritage management, focusing on both tangible and intangible cultural assets. The policy stresses public awareness and youth engagement, ensuring long-term community involvement in heritage preservation.

In Istanbul, *Kültürel Mirasın Korunması* (Protection of Cultural Heritage) addresses the specific risk of natural disasters, particularly earthquakes, which threaten the city's historical sites. Managed by the Istanbul Governorship, this policy promotes resilience through risk assessment, structural reinforcement, and educational outreach. Although it does not explicitly reference EU policies, the framework aligns with UNESCO guidelines on disaster preparedness for cultural sites.

Finally, the *Greece-Bulgaria Cross-Border Cooperation Program* (INTERREG V-A Greece-Bulgaria Cooperation Programme 2014-2020) builds on the successes of the previous 2007-2013 programme to strengthen cultural and economic collaboration between Greece and Bulgaria. Funded by the EU, it prioritises cross-border cooperation through infrastructure development, cultural exchange, and sustainable tourism. The programme emphasises environmental protection, social inclusion, and economic growth in border regions, aiming to preserve shared cultural heritage while addressing challenges such as climate change. By fostering partnerships and leveraging joint expertise, the policy enhances regional stability and integration within the broader European framework.

9.3. The cross-border dimension

The cross-border dimension of the policies in the Greece-Bulgaria-Turkey border region is central to fostering shared cultural and economic initiatives, although the emphasis varies by policy. Greece's and Bulgaria's participation in the *INTERREG* program highlights a regional approach to building cross-border cultural and economic connections. This policy encourages collaboration on joint cultural heritage projects, with a particular focus on border regions that historically share cultural ties and face common environmental and socio-economic challenges. The program has supported cross-border festivals, heritage site preservation efforts, and professional exchanges that promote mutual understanding and cultural exchange between communities on either side of the border.

Similarly, the *Greece-Bulgaria Cross-Border Cooperation Program 2014-2020* explicitly mentions a cross-border regional dimension, promoting initiatives aimed at enhancing social cohesion and regional development. This program has been relevant in a variety of cross-border contexts, from shared infrastructure improvements that facilitate tourism and cultural access to initiatives that highlight and protect shared heritage sites along the border. This policy supports collaborative governance models, bringing together local municipalities and cultural institutions to work on projects that span national boundaries and encourage regional integration.

Turkey's focus in Eastern Thrace includes international cooperation in heritage preservation, particularly with Greece, though primarily at a local and municipal level. Policies such as *The Role of Local Governments in Protecting Cultural Heritage* facilitate cultural exchange by emphasizing common heritage and encouraging cross-border projects. Although not always explicitly tied to

EU directives, Turkey's policies align with UNESCO's international frameworks, facilitating broader collaboration on cultural heritage conservation in border regions.

9.4. Alignment with EU policies

The cross-border cultural policies in the Greece-Bulgaria-Turkey border region align closely with EU directives and broader European cultural policies, particularly in areas of regional cooperation, cultural sustainability, and heritage preservation. The *INTERREG Europe* initiative, which supports Greece and Bulgaria in fostering cultural collaboration, reflects EU priorities as outlined in the European Agenda for Culture and the Creative Europe program. By emphasizing cross-border cultural exchange, regional development, and collaborative heritage projects, the policy promotes European cohesion and strengthens shared cultural identities within EU member states. Additionally, the language used in the policy—focusing on sustainable heritage management and cultural connectivity—echoes EU goals for building cultural bridges across borders and supports the EU's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly those related to sustainable communities (SDG 11).

The *Greece-Bulgaria Cross-Border Cooperation Program* also aligns with EU frameworks by encouraging socio-economic integration and cultural connectivity in border areas. It supports EU objectives for regional development, specifically through initiatives that enhance cross-border infrastructure and promote cultural tourism. This policy's focus on heritage conservation and cultural accessibility underscores its alignment with EU guidelines, such as those seen in the European Heritage Label and the European Year of Cultural Heritage. The collaboration framework within this program mirrors the EU's commitment to cohesion and regional integration, supporting projects that celebrate and protect shared heritage in border areas.

In Turkey, while not an EU member, cultural policies in the Eastern Thrace region demonstrate alignment with EU values in heritage preservation and international cooperation. Policies such as *The Role of Local Governments in Protecting Cultural Heritage* reflect principles found in EU directives, emphasizing local engagement in heritage management and community-focused sustainability. By collaborating with EU-supported initiatives, Turkish policies facilitate cultural dialogue and shared heritage projects that are compatible with EU standards, promoting regional stability and cultural integration along the Greece-Turkey border.

These policies collectively illustrate an alignment with EU objectives for cultural diversity, heritage conservation, and cross-border cooperation. They also underscore a shared commitment to preserving cultural assets through sustainable management and international collaboration, enhancing both European and regional identities within the broader scope of EU and UNESCO standards for cultural heritage.

10. Cultural and cultural policies compared

This internal report provides a comprehensive analysis of cultural and cultural heritage policies relevant to the border regions included in the B-SHAPES project, marking an initial attempt at mapping these policies. The findings highlight significant diversity in the relevance and focus of policies across different levels of governance.

At the national level, cultural policies are often either not directly relevant to cross-border cooperation in this area (especially when the cultural policy is a state competence in federal states or has been devolved to regions in unitary states) or lack explicit references to the specific features of these territories as situated close to a border, a neighbouring country or being part of a borderland. Regional and local levels show greater variation, with some regions actively engaging in cross-border cultural initiatives while others do not. This inconsistency is also reflected in the role of cross-border cooperation itself—some regions prioritize cultural activities as part of their CBC efforts, while others neglect culture altogether.

Tourism frequently intersects with cultural policy, but as noted by Prokkola et al.¹⁰ in the context of Scandinavia, this connection does not consistently translate into actionable strategies or concrete measures. Notably, the most active engagement with cultural policies occurs in the Germany-Poland-Czechia border regions. Minority groups also emerge as significant drivers of cultural initiatives, particularly in South Tyrol and the Denmark-Germany border area, although this influence is less pronounced in the Hungarian-Slovak context.

In conclusion, the report demonstrates the fragmented and uneven landscape of cultural and cultural heritage policies across border regions, emphasizing the need for greater alignment and attention to cross-border cultural dynamics.

¹⁰ Prokkola, E. K., Andersen, D. J., Jakola, F., Nilson, T., & Svensson, S. M. H. (2024). Multilayered Borders as a Method for Studying Tourism Destinations: A Case of Northern European Border Regions. *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 1-21.

Annex: List of policies

Finland- Sweden border case

1. **Valtakunnallisesti arvokkaat maisema-alueet (Nationally valuable landscape areas), Eteläinen Lappi (2021)**
Finland, Finnish, Landscape Inventory
National, Ministry of Environment, Cultural Environment / Nature Protection and Conservation
[Link to Policy](#)
2. **Joen ja meren rajakaupunki: Tornion kulttuuriympäristöohjelma (The Program for Cultural Environment in Tornio), 2012**
Finland, Finnish, Strategy
Municipal, Ministry of Environment, Nature Protection and Conservation
[Link to Policy](#)
3. **Lappi-sopimus, Lapin maakuntaohjelma 2022-2025 (The Development Program for Lapland) Finland, Finnish, Strategy**
Regional, The Regional Council of Lapland, Regional Development
[Link to Policy](#)
4. **Norrbottens kulturmiljöprogram 2010-2020 (Norrbotten's Cultural Environment Program 2010-2020)**
Sweden, Swedish, Strategy
Regional, Länsstyrelsen Norrbotten, Cultural Policy, Environmental and Conservation Policy and Planning
[Link to Policy](#)
5. **Regional utvecklingsstrategi Norrbotten 2030 (Regional Development Strategy for Norrbotten 2030)**
Sweden, Swedish, Strategy
Regional, Länsstyrelsen Norrbotten, Regional Development and Cultural Policy
[Link to Policy](#)
6. **Kulturplan Haparanda kommun (Cultural Plan for Haparanda Municipality) Sweden, Swedish, Plan**
Local (Municipality), Haparanda Municipality, Cultural Policy
[Link to Policy](#)
7. **Tornionlaakson neuvosto: Kohti Euroopan yhtenäisintä raja-alueetta. Strategia 2024-2030 (The Council of Torne Valley: Towards Europe's Most Integrated Border Region. Strategy 2024-2030)**
Finland-Sweden-Norway, Finnish/Swedish, Strategy
Regional (Cross-Border), The Council of Torne Valley (Municipal-based Cooperation Organization), Regional Development

Sweden-Denmark border case

1. **Ekendtgørelse af lov om bygningsfredning og bevaring af bygninger og bymiljøer**
Denmark, Danish, Legislative/Policy
National, Ministry of Culture, Cultural Heritage Conservation
[Link to Policy](#)
2. **Bekendtgørelse om Det Særlige Bygningssyn**
Denmark, Danish, Regulatory
National, Ministry of Culture, Cultural Heritage Conservation
[Link to Policy](#)
3. **Bekendtgørelse om henlæggelse af opgaver og beføjelser til Kulturarvsstyrelsen**
Denmark, Danish, Regulatory
National, Ministry of Culture, Cultural Heritage Management
[Link to Policy](#)
4. **Lov om ændring af lov om sikring af kulturværdier i Danmark**
Denmark, Danish, Legislative/Policy
National, Ministry of Culture, Cultural Heritage Protection and Law Enforcement
[Link to Policy](#)
5. **Bekendtgørelse af lov om støtte til folkeoplysende voksenundervisning, frivilligt folkeoplysende foreningsarbejde og daghøjskoler samt om Folkeuniversitetet (folkeoplysningsloven)**
Denmark, Danish, Legislative/Policy

- National, Ministry of Culture, Education and Culture
[Link to Policy](#)
6. **Lov om visse medietjenesteudbyderes bidrag til fremme af dansk kultur**
 Denmark, Danish, Legislative/Policy
 National, Ministry of Culture, Education and Culture
[Link to Policy](#)
 7. **Kultur, der gør en forskel; KULTURPOLITIK FOR HELSINGØR KOMMUNE**
 Denmark, Danish, Cultural Policy
 Local (municipality), Helsingør Municipality, Tourism and Cultural Heritage Policies
[Link to Policy](#)
 8. **Aalborg Kommunes Kulturpolitik (Aalborg Municipality's Cultural Policy)**
 Denmark, Danish, Cultural Policy
 Local (municipality), Aalborg Municipality, Culture, Arts, Public Spaces, Social Cohesion
[Link to Policy](#)
 9. **Kulturaftale 2021-2024 (Cultural Agreement 2021-2024)**
 Denmark, Danish, Cultural Agreement
 Regional, Danish Ministry of Culture (in collaboration with regional municipalities), Cultural Development, Regional Collaboration
[Link to Policy](#)
 10. **Regional Kulturplan För Skåne 2021–2024 (Regional Cultural Policy for Scania 2021-2024)**
 Sweden, Swedish, Cultural Plan
 Regional, Skåne Municipality, Cultural
[Link to Policy](#)
 11. **Kulturstrategiskt Program 2024–2030 (Cultural Strategic Program 2024–2030)**
 Sweden, Swedish, Cultural Strategy
 Local (municipality), Malmö Stad / City, Culture, Urban Development, Sustainability
[Link to Policy](#)
 12. **Malmö Kulturstrategi 2014–2020 (Malmö Cultural Strategy 2014–2020)**
 Sweden, Swedish, Cultural Strategy
 Local (municipality), Malmö Stad / City, Culture, Urban Development, Sustainability
[Link to Policy](#)
 13. **Regional kulturplan för Skåne 2025–2028 (Regional Cultural Plan for Scania 2025-2028)**
 Sweden, Swedish, Cultural Policy
 Regional, Skåne Municipality, Culture, Regional Development, Sustainability
[Link to Policy](#)

Denmark- German Case

1. **Kulturarv (Cultural Heritage)**
 Denmark, Danish, National Directive and Law
 National, Ministry, Cultural Policies
[Link to Policy](#)
2. **Kulturkompasset (Cultural Compass)**
 Denmark, Danish, Municipal Strategy
 Municipal, Municipality, Cultural Administration
[Link to Policy](#)
3. **Kultur im Dialog - Kulturpolitische Leitlinien (Culture in Dialogue - Cultural Policy Guidelines)**
 Germany, German, State (Bundesland) Strategy
 State, Ministry, Cultural
[Link to Policy](#)
4. **Flensburg 2030+**
 Germany, German, Municipal Strategy
 Municipal, Municipality, Cultural
[Link to Policy](#)
5. **Leeuwarden Declaration**
 Netherlands, Denmark, and Germany, English/German/Danish/Dutch, Trilateral Declaration
 State, Ministries, Environment and Nature Conservation
[Link to Policy](#)

6. Kulturfokus DK-DE

Denmark and Germany, Danish/German, Cross-border Agreement
State, Regional, and Municipal, Cultural

[Link to Policy](#)

Germany-France case

1. Politique culturelle transfrontalière et européenne de la Région Grand Est

France, French, Plan

Regional, Region, Cultural Policies in the Area of Cultural Heritage

[Link to Policy](#)

2. Le Forum Culture de la Conférence du Rhin supérieur

France, Germany, Switzerland, French and German, Forum

Regional / Land (in the three countries), Region, Cultural

[Link to Policy](#)

3. Fonds culturel transfrontalier - Rhin supérieur

France, Germany, Switzerland, French and German, Cross-border Agreement

Region / Land / EGTC, EGTC, Cultural

[Link to Policy](#)

German-Poland-Czechia Case

1. Strategy of Development, Lower Silesia Voivodeship

Poland, Polish, Cultural Strategy

Regional, Regional Parliament (Sejmik) of Lower Silesia Voivodeship, General Strategy of Development

[Link to Policy](#)

2. Cross-border cooperation strategy of Cieszyn and Český Těšín in the context of the development of the Cieszyn Silesia Euroregion

Poland / Czech Republic, Polish / Czech, Cross-border Strategy

Cross-border, Local Governments, Comprehensive Development Strategy

[Link to Policy](#)

3. Strategy of the Neisse-Nisa-Nysa Euroregion 2021-2027

Poland / Czech Republic / Germany, Polish, Cross-border Strategy

Cross-border, Euroregional, Local and Regional Governments, Comprehensive Development Strategy

[Link to Policy](#)

4. Development Strategy of the City Zgorzelec for the Years 2015-2025

Poland, Polish, Municipal Strategy

Municipal, Local Authority, Comprehensive Development Strategy

[Link to Policy](#)

5. Transnational cooperation for the sustainable development within the EGTC Muskau Bend

Poland / Germany, Polish / German, Convention and Charter

Transnational, 14 Polish and German Local Authorities, Cross-Border Cooperation Policies, Nature Protection and Conservation

[Link to Policy](#)

[Additional Link](#)

6. Development strategy of the Cieszyn Silesia Euroregion for 2021-2027

Poland / Czech Republic, Polish / Czech, Cross-border Strategy

Cross-border, Euroregional, Local Governments, Comprehensive Development Strategy

[Link to Policy](#)

7. "Vision 2030". Action and Development Plan of the Spree-Neisse-Bóbr Euroregion for 2021-2027

Poland / Germany, Polish, Cross-border Plan

Cross-border, Euroregional, 1 Polish and 1 German Association (Partners of the Agreement on the

Establishment of the Spree-Neisse-Bóbr Euroregion) Representing Local Governments, Comprehensive

Development Plan

[Link to Policy](#)

8. Polish-German Cross-Border Tourism Development Concept in the Gubin-Guben Eurocity

Poland / Germany, Polish, Cross-border Concept

Cross-border, Local Governments, Tourism Development Concept

No Link

9. **Cultural Development Planning 2020-2030 for the Town of Görlitz**
Germany, German, Cultural Development Strategy
Municipal, Town of Görlitz, Cultural Heritage
[Link to Policy](#)
10. **Culture Compass: Signpost for Culture Development in Saxony**
Germany, German, Guidelines
Regional, Saxon State Ministry for Science and Arts, Tourism and Cultural Heritage Policies, Education, Sustainability
[Link to Policy](#)
11. **Strategy of Development, Liberec Region**
Czechia, Czech, Strategy
Regional, Regional Office of Liberec Region, General Strategy of Development
[Link to Policy](#)
12. **ACT of 6 January 2005 on National and Ethnic Minorities and on the Regional Languages**
Poland, Polish/English, Act/Law
National, Department of Religious Denominations and National and Ethnic Minorities, Cultural Heritage Policies
[Link to Policy](#)
13. **Regional Development Strategy of the Czech Republic 2021+**
Czech Republic, English (translation from Czech), Strategic Framework
National, Ministry of Regional Development, Czech Republic, Regional Development, Economic Competitiveness, Cultural Heritage
[Link to Policy](#)
14. **Strategic Framework Czech Republic 2030**
Czech Republic, English (translated from Czech), Strategic Framework for Sustainable Development
National, Office of the Government of the Czech Republic, Department of Sustainable Development, Social, Economic, Environmental, Regional Development, Cultural Heritage
[Link to Policy](#)
15. **State Cultural Policy of the Czech Republic 2021–2025+**
Czech Republic, Czech (with an English summary), Strategic Framework
National, Ministry of Culture, Czech Republic, Cultural Heritage, Arts, Creative Industries, Regional Development
[Link to Policy](#)
16. **Development Program for Period from 2017 (Updated in 2023)**
Czech Republic, Czech (with an English summary), Regional Development Plan
Cross-border, Municipality of Hrádek nad Nisou, Cultural Heritage, Tourism, Cross-Border Cooperation

Hungarian - Slovak border Case

1. **Komárom-Esztergom County Spatial Development Strategic and Operative Programs**
Hungary, Hungarian, Spatial Development Program
Regional, County, Spatial Development
[Link to Policy](#)
2. **Law resulting in the establishment of a commissioned foundation operating the Central European Built Heritage Protection Foundation (KEÉÖMA)**
Hungary, Hungarian, Law
(Macro)regional, Government of Hungary, Management of Built Cultural Heritage
[Link to Policy](#)

Italy-Austria case

1. **Charter of the Museums of the Euroregion Tyrol-South Tyrol-Trentino for Sustainable Development**
Italy/Austria, German/Italian, Guidelines
Transnational/Regional, Euroregion Tyrol-South Tyrol-Trentino, Sustainability and Cultural Heritage
[Link to Policy](#)
2. **Decision on the Euregio Museum Year 2021**
Italy/Austria, German/Italian, Decision/Agreement
Transnational/Regional, Euroregion Tyrol-South Tyrol-Trentino, Cultural Heritage Policies, Cross-Border

Cooperation Policies

[Link to Policy](#)

3. **Handbook for the Protection of Cultural Assets**
Italy/Austria, German/Italian, Guidelines
Regional, Autonomous Province of Bozen/Bolzano, Cultural Heritage Policies, Sustainability and Cultural Heritage, Disaster Risk Management
[Link to Policy](#)
4. **National Plan for the Digitalisation of Cultural Heritage**
Italy, Italian, Plan/Guidelines
National, Italian Ministry of Culture, Digitalization and Technology Policies, Cultural Heritage Policies
[Link to Policy](#)
5. **Federal Guidelines for Cultural Policies**
Austria, German, Guidelines
National, Austrian Ministry of Culture, Cultural Heritage Policies, Sustainability and Cultural Heritage, Research, and Innovation
[Link to Policy](#)
6. **Local Development Strategy Pustertal 2023-2027**
Italy, Italian/German, Strategy
Regional/Local, Regional Development Agency Pustertal, Tourism and Cultural Heritage Policies, Nature Protection and Conservation, Sustainability and Cultural Heritage, Regional Development
[Link to Policy](#)

Bulgaria-Greece-Turkey case

1. **Κλιματική Αλλαγή και Πολιτιστική Κληρονομιά (Climate Change and Cultural Preservation)**
Greece, Greek, Cultural Policy
National, Ministry of Culture and Sports (in coordination with other relevant bodies), Cultural Heritage, Climate Change Adaptation, Environmental Protection
Protected file
2. **Πολιτιστική Κληρονομιά και Βιωσιμότητα: Πρακτικός Οδηγός (Cultural Heritage and Sustainability: Practical Guide)**
Greece, Greek, Cultural Policy
Regional/International (as part of the INTERREG Europe project), INTERREG Europe, Cultural Heritage, Sustainable Development, Regional Development
[Link to Policy](#)
3. **Ανθεκτικότητα και πολιτιστική κληρονομιά των πόλεων. Μια στρατηγική για την πόλη της Θεσσαλονίκης (Resilience and Cultural Heritage of Cities: A Strategy for the City of Thessaloniki)**
Greece, Greek, Cultural Policy
Local (municipality), Municipality of Thessaloniki, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Cultural Heritage, Urban Planning, Sustainability
[Link to Policy](#)
4. **Ετήσιο Σχέδιο Δράσης 2024 (Annual Action Plan 2024)**
Greece, Greek, Cultural Policy
National, Ministry of Culture and Sports, Cultural Heritage Preservation and Promotion
[Link to Policy](#)
5. **National Cultural Policy of Bulgaria Regarding the Relationship “Culture – Development”**
Bulgaria, Bulgarian, Cultural Policy
National, Ministry of Culture, Bulgaria, Cultural Heritage, Economic Development, Social Cohesion
6. **Strategy for the Development of Bulgarian Culture 2019-2029**
Bulgaria, Bulgarian, Cultural Development Strategy
National, Ministry of Culture, Bulgaria, Cultural Heritage, Arts, Creative Industries
[Link to Policy](#)
7. **Kültürel Mirasın Korunmasında Yerel Yönetimlerin Rolü (The Role of Local Governments in Protecting Cultural Heritage)**
Turkey, Turkish, Cultural Heritage Preservation Policy
National and Local, UCLG-MEWA (United Cities and Local Governments Middle East and West Asia), Cultural Heritage, Local Government, Sustainability
[Link to Policy](#)

8. **Kültürel Mirasın Korunması (Protection of Cultural Heritage)**

Turkey, Turkish, Cultural Heritage Protection Strategy

National and Regional, Istanbul Valiliği (Istanbul Governorship) and other coordinating bodies, Culture, Disaster Risk Management, Urban Development

[Link to Policy](#)

9. **Greece-Bulgaria Cross-Border Cooperation Program 2014-2020**

Greece/Bulgaria, Greek/Bulgarian, Cultural Policy

Regional, Cross-Border, European Union (in partnership with national and local governments of Greece and Bulgaria), Regional Development, Infrastructure, Cultural Exchange, Environment, Economic Growth

[Link to Policy](#)